

ROLE OF POST APPROVAL CLINICAL TRIALS FOR DRUG SAFETY***Siri Chandana Katakam**

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ABSTRACT

Following the drug-approval process, concerns remain regarding the safety of new drugs that are introduced into the marketplace. In the case of rare adverse events, the number of subjects that are treated in randomized controlled trials is invariably inadequate to determine the safety of the new pharmaceutical. Identifying safety signals for new and/or existing drugs is a major priority in the protection of public health. Unfortunately, design, analysis, and available data are often quite limited for detecting in a timely fashion any potentially harmful effects of drugs. In this review, we examine a variety of approaches for determining the possibility of adverse drug reactions. Our review includes spontaneous reports, meta-analysis of randomized controlled clinical trials, ecological studies, and analysis of medical claims data. We

consider both experimental design and analytic problems as well as potential solutions. Many of these methodologies are then illustrated through application to data on the possible relationship between taking antidepressants and increased risk of suicidality.

KEYWORDS: Poisson regression, propensity scores, adverse events, meta-analysis, mixed-effects models, suicide.

INTRODUCTION

Post-marketing studies are a major activity in the life cycle of a licensed drug/medicinal product and are regularly conducted by pharmaceutical companies and contract research organisations. Regulatory agencies rely on such industry funded studies for surveillance of

drug safety. In particular, the detection of “rare” (1 in 1000) and “very rare” (1 in 10 000) adverse drug reactions is often possible only with post-marketing studies.^[1]

According to the German Medicinal Products Act (Arzneimittelgesetz, AMG) all companies initiating a post-marketing study in the German drug market are required by law to register their study. The act specifies that the purpose of such studies is to investigate the use of medicinal products in daily routine, to assess rare adverse drug reactions, and to improve long term drug safety.^[2] To our knowledge there is no such law in other countries requiring all post-marketing studies to be registered, and there is considerable variation in the definition of such studies and the scope of registration in other EU countries.^[3] In this context, it should be of note that drug licensing and pharmacovigilance activities have been harmonised in the EU since 2001.^[4]

In the US, regulatory approval and registration of some post-marketing studies is required (such as interventional studies that must be registered under the US Food and Drug Administration Amendments Act of 2007)^[5], but, unlike Germany, not all post-marketing studies have to be registered.

In light of the documented lack of knowledge about rare adverse drug reactions from pre-marketing randomised controlled trials^[6] and systematic under-reporting of spontaneous reporting schemes,^[7] German regulators,^[8] physician bodies,^[9,10] and statutory health insurers^[11] have re-emphasised the importance and necessity of post-marketing studies for evaluating newly authorised drugs.

Despite Germany requiring the registration of all post-marketing studies, little is known on their size, cost, and nature. We therefore initiated freedom of information requests to obtain registration documents to understand the current state of post-marketing studies and evaluate whether these studies meet the aims specified in the Medicinal Products Act, particularly their potential to assess rare adverse drug reactions and thus help improve long term drug safety.

Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) have been considered the gold standard to demonstrate efficacy since the 1960s.^[12,13] While current routes to market for investigational drugs typically require at least two pivotal RCTs, these are time-consuming, costly, and produce evidence that can have limited applicability in real-world clinical practice. There is,

therefore, a move towards investigating innovative ways to improve the efficiency of clinical research.^[14,15]

The controlled nature of an RCT offers advantages in evidence generation as there are standard methods to reduce bias (like random-inaction and blinding), and they have comprehensive measurement of outcomes to demonstrate efficacy against both active and placebocontrols.^[16]

However, RCTs do not accurately reflect real-world circumstances under which patients are treated; thus, there is often need for observational studies to support additional evidence generation, particularly around questions of safety. Real-world data (RWD) forms the basis for real-world evidence(RWE) and can be extracted from a broad range of sources such as patient registries, health care databases, claims databases, patient net-works, social media, and patient-generated data from wearables.^[17-20] The definitions of RWD and RWE are relatively consistent between key regulatory agencies (see Table 1).^[21]

While RWE from observational studies is well accepted for post-approval safety monitoring and to answer pharmacy economic questions^{3, [22,23]} its contribution to regulatory decisions around effectiveness has been more limited. Indeed, evidence quality can be compromised by confounding by indications or a general lack of rigorous collection standards. There is, therefore, a need for the development of novel trial methodologies that can take the best parts of traditional RCT and observational study designs to produce RWE that provides adequate scientific evidence for regulatory decision-making. It has already been recognised byhealth authorities that there is a wide spectrum of potential uses ford/RWE in clinical studies, some of which preserve key features such as randomization.

THE EMERGING RULES FOR RWE THATIS FIT FOR REGULATORY PURPOSES

The 21st Century Cures Act and PDUFA VI requires the FDA to accelerate drug development and approval processes, and more specifically, to produce guidance on how to incorporate patient perspectives and innovative study designs, including RWE, into the drug development process. The recently published FDA framework for evaluation of how RWE can be incorporated into the regulatory approval process highlights the key topics for which full evaluation will be undertaken.

There is a need to define the rules for RWE that is fit for regulatory purposes. However, while the development of innovative trial designs is being actively encouraged by the major regulatory agencies, particularly with the FDA's Complex Innovative Trial Designs Pilot Program and Clinical Trials Transformation Initiative and the EMA's adaptive pathways initiative, the required standards to produce RWE that is acceptable for regulatory decision-making havenot yet been fully defined. Although regulators are open top roposals for studies with RWD and receiving RWE, the decision topursue an innovative study design as part of a clinical development program and regulatory approval strategy is not straightforward, asthe routes to obtaining pilot guidance are complex and the “rules” for acceptance of evidence in regulatory decision-making are not yet firmly defined. It is therefore essential to engage with regulatory authorities early to obtain alignment on objectives, inform the study design, and ensure the study design and data are acknowledged as “fit-for-purpose” before conducting a study that may not meet the regulatory goals.

To aid this process, several stakeholders have published frame-works and recommendations for the creation of RWE suitable for use in regulatory decisions. The Duke-Margolis Center for Health Pol-icy, with support from the FDA, released a white paper on the regulatory use of RWE in 2017 following open consultation with academics, patients, and industry.⁴⁸Emphasizing considerations for developing RWE that is fit for regulatory purposes, they identified several areas for practical improvement, including the need to ensure that the appropriate RWD sources are matched with appropriate study designs and data collection and handling methods to address the research question. They also encourage the formation of transparent collaborations and the sharing of datasets. Professional societies have also weighed in here too, with the International Society for Pharmaco economics and Outcomes Research and the International Society for Pharmacoepidemiology publishing recommendations for good procedural practices for RWE, aiming to build trust and expandits current use in health care decision-making. Many of the recom-mendations made in these aforementioned publications have been formalized in the FDA framework document.

An important part of planning innovative studies to produce RWE that provides adequate scientific evidence for regulatory decision-making is preparation of a thorough analytical plan at the outset ofthe study. This is already an integral part of most traditional pivotaland post-safety trials and should reasonably be extended to effective-ness studies that use RWD. Some also argue that pivotal and safety outcome RCTs and observational post authorization

safety studies should be registered on appropriate repositories (eg, ClinicalTrials.gov or the EU PAS Register) prior to study initiation as a requirement of the regulatory process. Whether RWE studies will be required to be registered in such a way is a topic of ongoing debate, with opinions sharply divided. Registration by itself is no guarantee of study quality, and any benefit from registration would be heavily dependent on what information would be required to be posted (eg, study protocols, methodological details, etc.). Further discussions between stake-holders will be required before a consensus develops.

In a separate framework on the regulatory use of RWE, Dreyer(2018) has discussed the requirement and transferability of key RCT study design elements to real-world studies. This builds on the current thinking around clinical outcomes from RWD analysis, suggesting that outcomes should be patient-centric and should be observable and relevant to daily clinical practice. Specific issues are addressed, such as blinding, which is routinely used in RCTs, but is often impractical to achieve under “real-world” circumstances, especially when comparing pharmacologic and nonpharmacologic treatments and when using a selection of “standard of care” comparators, which differ by locale, and while informative, would be impossible to blind. Furthermore, blinding might not be necessary for objective outcomes such as the results of a blood tests and imaging, for example, where in most cases, third-party raters, such as pathologists, are essentially blinded to treatment. The importance of using data sources that are “fit for purpose” and the familiarity of researchers with potential sources of bias or error so that the most appropriate study methodology is employed is also emphasized. Analytical methods should be transparent, defined up front, and optimized to answer the research question.

Regulators and industry have acknowledged the value of scientifically rigorous and innovative study methodologies as the key route to achieving the standard of substantial evidence for RWE. As a means to achieve this, the FDA framework proposes that the following should be considered: (a) whether the RWD are fit for use; (b) whether the trial or study design used to generate RWE can provide adequate scientific evidence to answer or help answer the regulatory question; (c) whether the study conduct meets FDA regulatory requirements (eg, for study monitoring and data collection).⁸ It should be noted that strict applicability of these rules, particularly for monitoring, is rarely feasible for studies that rely on existing data, since the identities of patient and care providers are masked to protect privacy in most secondary data sources.

Similarly, the EMA in its recent report on the use of large datasets for RWE made several recommendations to improve the quality of RWE, including the need to define standard formats for documenting datasets, protocols, and tools used to ensure study reproducibility. In addition, it emphasizes the need to ensure that outcome measures from novel data sources such as wearables should be reflective of a defined clinical benefit. If these considerations and recommendations are fully addressed by novel study methodologies, the quality of RWE will improve, and studies using RWD could increasingly be used in support of decisions about therapeutic effectiveness. The development of sufficiently robust RWE will ultimately depend on the ability of experts such as pharmacoepidemiologists, statisticians, data scientists, and academics to develop these new methodologies to optimize hybrid study designs, RWD collection and analysis in a way that is compliant with our current understanding of best practice for RWE generation, and open to regulatory scrutiny. Sponsors and data owners should proactively identify and develop standard operating procedures to be prepared for FDA audits and oversight by defining requirements for record retention, auditing, and patient privacy.

MODERNIZING THE CLASSICAL RCT

Some specific hybrid study designs under consideration for regulatory decision-making by the FDA fall into three broad categories: (a) investigational new drug submissions for RCTs that use RWD to capture clinical outcomes or safety data, including pragmatic and large simple trials; (b) protocols for single-arm trials that use external controls; (c) clinical trials using RWE to fulfil a post-marketing requirement for further evaluation of safety or effectiveness to support a regulatory decision.

PRAGMATIC AND LARGE SIMPLE TRIALS

Pragmatic and large simple trials mirror many of the features of RCTs including randomization but are typically very large RCTs and enable broader patient group to participate. These trials are increasingly being used to demonstrate effectiveness in a daily clinical practice setting and allow more clinically meaningful outcomes to be studied, creating readily transferable benefits for patients. This notion links in with the ever-developing narrative around patient-centric care and the increasing involvement of patients in the drug development process, aiming to increase the relevance of new therapeutic interventions to the patient experience.^{52,53} One of the first examples of a large simple trial was the Salk polio vaccine field trial of 1954, which led to regulatory approval of the vaccine

and a nationwide public health response to eradicate polio. More recently, the feasibility of pragmatic trials was also tested by the label expansion achieved for Janssen's INVEGASUSTENNA (Case study 3) that was based on the findings of the Paliperidone Palpitate Research in Demonstrating Effectiveness (PRIDE) trial which was designed to include treatment randomization and pragmatic outcomes. The trial was uniquely designed to mirror the population of adults living with serious and poorly controlled schizophrenia that health care professionals commonly see in clinical practice.

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is the major cause of mortality and morbidity in the USA and growing cause of chronic disease globally. The current pharmacological therapies for COPD, such as corticosteroids and β_2 agonists, may provide symptom relief, reduce the rate of exacerbations, hospitalisations and possibly mortality, but despite this, many patients still experience symptoms, exacerbations and disease progression. Although the exact cellular mechanisms underlying COPD pathogenesis are not completely understood, the consensus is that oxidative stress and inflammation induced by exposure to cigarette smoke or other environmental or occupational hazards are responsible for development of COPD.^[24] Therefore, a nutraceutical with potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties and relatively few side effects could be an attractive treatment option for COPD.

Quercetin (3,3',4',5,7-pentahydroxyflavone) is a dietary flavonoid and has potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. We have demonstrated that oral treatment with a low dose of quercetin decreases inflammation, oxidative stress and matrix metalloproteinase production in a mouse model of COPD.^[25] Quercetin supplemented diet also alleviates rhinovirus-induced lung inflammation in mice with COPD phenotype.^[26] Recent studies have also demonstrated amelioration of hyperglycaemia, reduction of blood pressure and improvement of cardiovascular health by inhibiting platelet aggregation in experimental models.

Accumulating epidemiological evidence suggests that quercetin-rich diets are associated with lower incidence of asthma^[27] and reduce disease severity in subjects with COPD.^[28] Treatment with quercetin decreased markers of oxidative stress and inflammation in plasma of patients with pulmonary sarcoidosis, another chronic lung inflammatory disease driven by oxidative stress.^[29,30] In another study, quercetin was shown to reduce blood pressure and plasma lipids in overweight or obese subjects with a high cardiovascular disease risk.^[31] Daily intake of quercetin-rich onion peel extract (equivalent to 100 mg of

quercetin/day) for 10 weeks decreased blood pressure, serum lipids and blood glucose levels in male smokers.^[32] Additionally, treatment with quercetin for 12 weeks reduced the risk of acquiring upper respiratory infection in a large population of healthy adults.^[33] The latter study also suggests that quercetin treatment in healthy volunteers has no adverse effects. Furthermore, a meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials indicated treatment with quercetin reduces plasma C reactive protein^[34] and blood pressure in hypertensive subjects.^[35] despite these epidemiological and experimental pieces of evidence, there have been no clinical trials examining the therapeutic effects of quercetin in COPD. An objective of this study was to determine the safety of quercetin supplementation in patients with COPD, because it is the first step towards using quercetin as a therapeutic agent in these patients.

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most common sustained heart rhythm disorder with an increasing worldwide prevalence. Following seminal studies identifying the pulmonary veins (PVs) as the primary triggering sites of origin for AF, catheter-based electrical isolation of the PVs has emerged as an effective means to treat AF. Both procedural technique and catheter ablation technology—using either radiofrequency, cryothermal or laser energy—have improved over time such that AF is now the most commonly ablated arrhythmia. Indeed, clinical data support its use as first-line therapy to not only improve quality of life, but also mortality in heart failure patients, and, in concert with antiarrhythmic drugs, significantly decrease the rates of stroke and mortality in a broad spectrum of AF patients. Despite improvements in procedural outcomes, there remain safety considerations including stroke, PV stenosis, phrenic nerve palsy, pericardial tamponade and atrio-oesophageal fistula—the latter being the most dreaded complication because of an 50% rate of associated mortality. These complications highlight the weak link shared among all thermal energy-based ablation platforms: as the ablative heat (or cold) wave propagates through tissue, its destructive effect is tissue indiscriminate. Thus, collateral damage to surrounding tissue is the potential price paid for ablation transmural. In contrast, pulsed field ablation (PFA) is a novel ablation modality that, in pre-clinical and clinical studies, has displayed preferential tissue ablation. Pulsed field ablation involves the application of ultra-rapid (microseconds to nanoseconds) electrical pulses to generate strong electrical fields causing, among other effects, irreversible nanoscale pore formation and, ultimately, cellular death. Pre-clinical and clinical studies have demonstrated that by optimizing voltage amplitude, phasic waveforms and pulse sequences, one can completely avoid damage to peri-cardiac structures such as the

oesophagus and phrenic nerve. While there are several PFA catheter technologies in development, the technology with the greatest amount of pre-clinical and clinical evidence is the multi electrode pent spline PFA catheter— also the only PFA catheter with regulatory approval (CE Mark). This pent spline PFA catheter has been studied in both paroxysmal AF patients in the IMPULSE, PEFCAT, and PEFCAT2 trials, and persistent AF patients in the Persephone trial. On the one hand, these trials demonstrated that AF ablation was not only feasible and effective, but the theoretical safety benefits observed preclinically were indeed realized in clinical practice. This included the absence of: (i) oesophageal damage as evaluated by oesophagi oduodenoscopy and thoracic MRI, (ii) phrenic nerve injury, or (iii) PV stenosis/narrowing. On the other hand, these studies included only a modest number of patients (150) and relatively few operators— raising the question of the pent spline PFA catheter safety profile in a large ‘real world’ environment. Since this technology commenced limited market utilization in March 2021, we conducted the MANIFEST-PF survey of its performance in an unselected patient population in routine clinical practice. We evaluated the catheter’s acute effectiveness and safety, including rare oesophageal effects not discernable after the treatment of only 150 patients, and unforeseen rare PFA-related complications.

Psoriasis (PsO), psoriatic arthritis (PsA) and ankylosing spondylitis (AS) result from a complex interplay among environmental, genetic and immune triggers. Treatment is typically intended for a long duration; therefore, understanding the long-term safety profile of therapeutic agents is essential for clinical decision-making.

Interleukin (IL)-17-mediated inflammation plays a pivotal role in the pathogenesis of chronic immune-mediated inflammatory diseases (IMIDs). Therapeutic blockade of the IL-17 pathway results in the inhibition of both pathological and physiological mechanisms. The IL-17 family members IL-17A and IL-17F have pleiotropic effects on multiple immune cell types and play an important role in host defence against infections (specifically fungal infections). Therefore, it is important to address the effect of IL-17 blockade on opportunistic infections.

The pathogenesis of PsO, PsA and AS share common systemic inflammatory pathways and cytokines. Because of the inflammatory disease burden and genetic overlap, patients with IMIDs are more susceptible to cardiovascular disease (CVD), metabolic comorbidities and inflammatory bowel diseases (IBDs) vs the general population. These comorbidities, along

with the concomitant medications used to treat these conditions, may affect the safety profile of treatments for PsO, PsA and AS.

Assessing the safety profile of a drug using data from multiple clinical trials and post-marketing experience across indications is best suited to identify risks that may become evident in a larger dataset. Secukinumab, a direct IL-17A inhibitor, has shown long-lasting efficacy and safety in treating the complete spectrum of psoriatic and spondyloarthritis (SpA) disease manifestations, including the nails, scalp, palms and soles, as well as PsA and axial SpA (axSpA).

Secukinumab is currently approved in more than 100 countries for use in PsO, PsA and axSpA. Over 20,000 patients have been treated with secukinumab in a clinical trial setting, and approximately 500,000 patients have been treated worldwide since launch. A longer-term report of pooled safety and tolerability data for secukinumab across the 3 indications (up to 5 years of treatment in PsO and PsA; up to 4 years in AS) was consistent with the safety profile observed in individual clinical trials.

This integrated safety assessment (ISA) in PsO, PsA and AS patients who received secukinumab treatment for up to 5 years included pooled clinical trial data and post-marketing safety surveillance data. The current report enhances the previously published pooled safety report with a larger dataset and longer exposure to secukinumab.

Biopharmaceutical companies and their development partners increasingly use data from real-world settings to generate evidence that can support regulatory decision making and approvals of their manufactured medical products. The use of such real-world evidence (RWE) can complement¹ or, in some cases, serve as an alternative to evidence traditionally yielded by randomized controlled trials (RCTs). For example, the use of external control arms³ can have considerable benefits, including accelerating the development process or reducing burden on trial participants. RWE can also provide investigators the opportunity to ask more questions and to understand broader, more diverse populations, as compared to RCTs.

The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA; also referred to here as the Agency) has taken significant steps to advance the use of RWE in regulatory decision making. This momentum has grown after the 21st Century Cures Act passed in December 2016; the act required FDA

to develop a program for evaluating the use of RWE to support new indications for already-approved drugs and fulfil post approval study requirements. In 2018, FDA published a framework for its RWE program and is currently drafting guidance on its regulatory expectations regarding the use of RWE in medical product approvals. As part of its broad impact, FDA's framework has helped to promote common definitions for real-world data (RWD; defined as "data relating to patient health status and/or the delivery of health care routinely collected from a variety of sources") and RWE (defined as "the clinical evidence about the usage and potential benefits or risks of a medical product derived from analysis of RWD"⁴). This is part of a worldwide interest in the use of RWE, including by regulatory agencies, such as the European Medicines Agency (EMA), the Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices Agency (PMDA) in Japan, and the National Medical Products Administration (NMPA) in China.

Much of FDA's regulatory use of RWE to date has been in the context of post market surveillance through programs like FDA's Sentinel initiative, a system initially designed to aid the Agency in evaluating medical product safety, and which has more recently expanded in scope. Current goals include enhancing Sentinel's ability to evaluate effectiveness⁸ and extending the evaluation of safety. In parallel, FDA also created a pilot project in 2008 to provide for the evaluation of vaccine effectiveness and, in 2017, launched the Biologics Effectiveness and Safety (BEST) system to enhance FDA's use and analysis of data to assure the safety and effectiveness of biological products.

Beyond post market surveillance, FDA considers RWE studies as part of the evidence package for submissions seeking authorization to market new medical products, including new drug applications (NDAs) and biologics license applications (BLAs). These submissions are reviewed and decisions are rendered primarily by two centers within the Agency: the Center for Drug Evaluation and Research (CDER), which focuses on drug products and therapeutic biological products, and the Center for Biologics Evaluation and Research (CBER), which focuses on biological products including vaccines. Studies submitted as part of a sponsor's overall evidence package will be considered in decision making. Approvals will then be based on, among other things, studies that provide "substantial evidence" (in CDER decisions) or "primary evidence" (in CBER decisions), which make the primary case for product safety and effectiveness, and "supportive evidence," which can serve to bolster the case. Submitted studies providing therapeutic context can help reviewers understand the

landscape of the disease (such as disease prevalence and incidence) and any current standard of care, but may not directly affect decision making. Many submitted studies will be presented in the FDA-approved product label of an approved or licensed drug or biological product. As such, RWE studies have the potential to be directly influential in prescribers' decision making if FDA approves a product label that includes submitted RWE studies.

FDA and others have directly and indirectly provided insights into FDA's current approaches by speaking to and publishing select examples of successful and unsuccessful uses of RWE studies in medical product approvals, and FDA has provided publicly available guidance for industry and staff. However, RWE methodology is evolving, and on many important topics, RWE stakeholders lack a shared understanding of FDA's expectations around the use of RWE, particularly in the context of NDAs and BLAs.

To date, there are no published systematic assessments of the use of RWE studies in FDA-approved NDAs and BLAs, nor on FDA's feedback on and acceptance of such studies. In this paper, we address this gap by presenting a systematic review of FDA's written approval documents involving RWE studies in NDAs and BLAs to determine whether and how FDA incorporated that evidence in its final decision for approval. We summarize trends in recent use of RWE in FDA-approved NDAs and BLAs, as well as whether and how RWE supported FDA's approval decision. By distilling these reviews, we also seek to identify best practices for avoiding common design and analysis pitfalls identified by the Agency.

SARS-Cov-2, a member of the coronavirus family, has been ravaging the world for the past 18 months. Although an effective treatment has eluded the medical community, there have been several registered trials on finding new or repurposed drugs. Several studies have discussed the mechanism of the virus-host interaction and possible treatments³⁵, but safe and effective treatment for the disease is yet to emerge. Drug repurposing seems to be an immediate solution, and various drugs have been suggested for the COVID-19 treatment.^[36,37]

The drugs required to combat the pathogen may fall into one or more of the following categories: antivirals, anti-inflammatory agents, and supportive therapies.^[38,39] According to V'Kovski the antiviral action can be based on the stages of viral-host interactions. These include attachment and virus neutralisation, host protease inhibitors that stop the entry of the virus, viral protease inhibitors, viral RdRp inhibitors, and viral maturation inhibitors.

Frediansyah et al.^[40] enumerated the possible antiviral solutions at various stages of interactions. The role of cathepsin L in cleavage of the S protein complex and subsequent release of virus genome is well documented. Inhibiting cathepsin L inhibits the entry of SARS-Cov-2 by 76%.^[41]

Pro-inflammatory cytokine production is natural during the immune response. The elimination of virus-infected cells is an essential step in disease control. If this step, which naturally follows virus entry and replication, is defective or prolonged, it can result in a cytokine storm^[42], an uncontrolled release of pro-inflammatory cytokines. Several interleukins are involved in a cytokine storm, the foremost being interleukin 6 (IL-6), IL-1^[43], and IL-17.^[44] IL-17 also seems to have a role as the interaction partner of SARS-Cov-2. Therefore, anti-inflammatory drugs targeting the production of these interleukins are necessary for COVID-19 treatment.

INDOMETHACIN AS A DRUG FOR SARS-COV-2

Amici et al.^[45] were the first to identify the antiviral activity of indomethacin. They recorded the antiviral activities of indomethacin against SARS-Cov-1 in vitro. Xu et al.^[46] presented evidence of its antiviral activity against SARS-Cov-2. Their investigations covered the antiviral effect of indomethacin in vitro, cellular, corona-infected canine models. They also stated that indomethacin does not reduce infectivity, binding, or entry into target cells. This conclusion is based on the results of for SARS-Cov-1, although computer models have indicated otherwise.^[47] Downregulation of ACE2 and TMPRSS2 is important to reduce infectivity. Using an open-source code, Gene2Drug, Napolitano et al. showed in a computer model that indomethacin downregulates ACE2 by suppressing the genes in the ACE2 pathway. Raghav et al.^[48] depicted the role of indomethacin in inhibiting cathepsin L activity required for fusion. Interestingly, no other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs projected this quality.

Non-Structural Protein7 (Nsp7), along with Nsp12, is essential for RNA synthesis, as highlighted by recognised that prostaglandin E synthase 2 (PGES-2) is an “interactor” with Nsp7, and indomethacin inhibits PGES-2. Hence, indomethacin is an essential candidate for blocking RNA synthesis. reported this block of RNA synthesis. Amici et al.^[49] also demonstrated that protein kinase R (PKR) activation by indomethacin inhibits virus protein translation. This follows the work of Brunelli et al.^[50] where the role of indomethacin in activating PKR directly has been demonstrated.

Several publications^[51,52] have highlighted the importance of preventing inflammation in Covid-19 patients. For example, indomethacin downregulates IL-6 by inhibiting the synthesis of PGES-2.^[53] In addition, indomethacin has successfully contained cytokine reactions in kidney transplant patients receiving OKT3 therapy.^[54,55]

conducted one of the first indomethacin trials. The objective was to compare the data from open-label single-arm data for indomethacin; they showed the effect of indomethacin as a treatment option by matching propensity score with retrospectively collected data on paracetamol. Gordon et al. indicated by retrospective data analysis that indomethacin markedly reduces the need for hospitalisation. Two studies^[56] have shown the effectiveness of indomethacin in treating a small number of SARS-Cov-2 patients with severe comorbidities. However, these were small case series, and a larger controlled trial is required to validate these findings.

The primary objective of this study is to determine the percentage of desaturating patients as a quantitative criteria $SpO_2 \leq 93$ has been used as a measure. The secondary outcome was symptomatic relief. Time to become afebrile, relief from cough, and myalgia are the significant symptoms for the secondary outcome. The safety profile of indomethacin was also monitored as a secondary outcome.

RET fusions are identified in 1%-2% of patients with non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC).¹⁻ These fusions result in ligand-independent constitutive activation of the RET pathway and increased oncogenic signaling. Both selpercatinib and pralsetinib are selective RET inhibitors, which have demonstrated promising clinical activity in patients with *RET* fusion-positive NSCLCs. This underscores the benefit of including *RET* fusions as part of comprehensive oncogene driver testing in patients with NSCLCs.

On the basis of compelling and durable responses observed in the largest clinical study in RET-altered cancers, selpercatinib emerged as a new standard of care for patients with *RET*-altered lung and thyroid cancers. The drug was first approved in May 2020 by the US Food and Drug Administration for adult patients with *RET* fusion-positive NSCLCs and subsequently has gained regulatory approval in multiple geographies. Additional data regarding the drug's activity and safety, with increased patient numbers and longer follow-up, are valuable as more providers treat patients with this first-in-class, highly selective, and potent RET inhibitor.

In LIBRETTO-001, a registrational, phase I/II, single-arm, open-label study, selpercatinib demonstrated durable antitumor activity, including intracranial efficacy. In the initial registrational analysis set (n = 144), high response rates and favorable tolerability were observed in both treatment-naïve (n = 39) and platinum-based chemotherapy pretreated (n = 105) patients with *RET* fusion-positive advanced NSCLC. However, since the majority of patients were alive and progression-free at the time of initial approval, the median duration of response (DoR) and progression-free survival (PFS) could not be accurately estimated.

In this article, we provide an updated analysis of the activity of selpercatinib in *RET* fusion-positive NSCLC. This includes efficacy in a total of 316 patients (172 additional patients). Furthermore, we provide 18 more months of follow-up than that previously published.

CLINICAL BENEFIT AND QOL ASSOCIATED WITH APPROVED DRUGS

FDA and EMA criteria for drug approval require substantial evidence of clinical benefit from adequate and well-controlled trials. Efficacy should be demonstrated by extending OS and/or improving QoL or an established surrogate for at least one of these. The demonstration of longer survival remains the gold standard cancer trial outcome and the preferred regulatory endpoint, and its improvement is considered a direct measure of benefit to patients. QoL reflects patients' subjective feelings about their health and is assessed through patient-reported outcome (PROs) measures, including symptoms, functional status, and health-related QoL assessment tools. Although improvement in PROs has been considered an appropriate endpoint for regular approval by regulatory authorities, efficacy endpoints, rather than QoL, have been preferred. To date, the only drug approved exclusively based on QoL by the FDA has been mitoxantrone in 1996 as initial chemotherapy for the treatment of patients with advanced hormone-refractory prostate cancer based on an improvement in pain. For the majority of approvals based on a PRO efficacy claim, PRO measures have been used to support other more commonly used efficacy endpoints. Examples include the FDA and EMA approvals of ruxolitinib for myelofibrosis based on reduction in spleen size and myelofibrosis symptoms assessed with the Myelofibrosis Symptom Assessment Form version 2.0 and the FDA and EMA approvals of abiraterone acetate, in combination with prednisone, for the treatment of patients with metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer based on radiographic progression-free survival (PFS), a favorable trend in OS, and exploratory patient-reported pain data measured with the Brief Pain Inventory-Short Form.

Patient-Centered Drug Development in Oncology: What Is the Medical Oncology Community Perspective?

For the majority of patients with advanced cancer, the goal of cancer treatments is palliation. Although some drugs have been transformative, others are modest in improving patient outcomes. Salas-Vega and colleagues found that, of the 53 cancer drugs that were approved by the FDA and the EMA between 2003 and 2013, only 43% improved OS by at least 3 months, and 42% were associated with an increase in QoL; in addition, 45% exhibited an adverse safety profile. Other articles with longer follow-up corroborate these findings. Kim and Prasad found that, between 2008 and 2012, the FDA approved 36 cancer drugs for 54 indications, with 67% of approvals based on an intermediate endpoint. Among these, only 5 (14%) drugs subsequently showed evidence of improved OS in the postmarketing period, and 18 (50%) drugs did not prolong OS; for 13 (36%) drugs, the survival effects were unknown. In a further study, Rupp and Zuckerman evaluated QoL benefits in drugs that had not shown improved OS and reported that only one drug (8%) showed an improvement in QoL. A similar analysis by Davies and colleagues of drugs approved between 2009 and 2014 by the EMA showed that, of 48 cancer drugs approved for 68 indications, at the time of marketing, 35% improved OS, and 10% showed an improvement in QoL. Among those indications without evidence of survival or QoL at the time of market approval, only 7% were later shown to improve survival, and 11% reported benefit in QoL in the postmarketing period. In addition, historical overviews of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) in oncology have shown that the magnitude of benefit of new therapeutics has decreased over time. Paradoxically, despite the decrease in effect size, investigators reporting RCTs have become increasingly likely to strongly endorse the experimental agent as a new standard of care.

In response to the escalating costs of many anticancer drugs, in combination with concerns that advances in cancer therapy provide limited benefit to patients, professional bodies have created value frameworks to provide a standardized approach to define clinically meaningful outcomes. In 2014, ASCO's Cancer Research Committee published targets for clinically meaningful benefit in trials for four cancer types (pancreatic, lung, triple negative breast, and colon): OS improvements ranging from 2.5 to 6 months and PFS improvements ranging from 3 to 5 months. Kumar and colleagues expanded this concept of meaningful clinical benefit by defining clinically meaningful improvements as a relative improvement of 25% and an absolute increase of 2.5 months in PFS and/or OS compared with that achieved with standard noncurative treatments of solid cancers. They observed that only 53% and 19% cancer drugs

approved from October 2015 to March 2016 met the threshold for clinically meaningful improvements in PFS and OS, respectively. Clinical benefit scales developed subsequently included composite measures of clinical benefit, including efficacy and safety and tolerability. The most widely used frameworks for assessing the value of cancer drugs include the ASCO Value Framework (ASCO-VF) and the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO)-Magnitude of Clinical Benefit Scale (MCBS). Other frameworks covering different aspects of clinical benefit include the Institute for Clinical and Economic Review (ICER) Value Assessment Framework, the Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (MSKCC) Drug Abacus, and the National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN) Evidence Blocks.

Several groups have analyzed the value of cancer drugs approved by the FDA and using these tools. Vivot and colleagues applied ASCO-VF v2 and ESMO-MCBS v1.0 to 37 pivotal clinical trials supporting approval of new cancer drugs approved by the FDA in the noncurative setting from 2000 to 2015. Only 13 drugs (35%) met the ESMO-MCBS threshold for substantial clinical benefit. Using ASCO-VF, the median drug value score was 37 (range, 33.4 to 17). Our group has applied the original version of ESMO-MCBS to evaluate 105 prospective RCTs that supported FDA approval of 63 cancer drugs in 118 indications between 2006 and 2016. Results showed that only 44% of drugs met the ESMO-MCBS threshold for substantial clinical benefit. Interestingly, over time, there was a statistically significant improvement in the number of trials meeting the ESMO-MCBS thresholds for substantial clinical benefit, in part because of more frequent reporting of improved QoL and/or fewer high-grade toxicities in later years. Applying the updated ESMO-MCBS v1.1 to the same cohort, including single-arm trials that supported FDA approval, showed that only 34% of drugs met the criteria for substantial clinical benefit. For single-arm trials, only 7% of drugs met the threshold for substantial clinical benefit, reflecting a lack of supporting data benefit in drugs evaluated in single-arm studies or unrealistic thresholds in the ESMO framework. Similar data have been reported for drugs approved by the EMA. Grössmann and colleagues applied the original version of the ESMO-MCBS to 70 trials supporting cancer drug approvals for 38 drugs by the EMA from 2011 to 2016. Only 15 (21%) of the 70 investigated indications met the thresholds for substantial clinical benefit. Similar data were reported by Davis and colleagues. When the magnitude of clinical benefit has been compared with drug costs, concerning results have been found: a dissociation between drug cost and outcomes and clinical benefit and even an inverse relation between clinical benefit and drug cost.

Unsurprisingly, when the ASCO-VF and ESMO-MCBS framework scores have been compared, the degrees of concordance are low to moderate, suggesting that the two frameworks differ with respect to what represents substantial benefit. Indeed, the challenge lies in how to capture a substantial clinical benefit in a single metric and the weight applied by each framework to efficacy, safety, and QoL outcome measures. Further, a crucial aspect to be taken into account is that these frameworks have been developed in response to the substantial increase in financial costs of new treatments, allowing payers to prioritize high-value drugs. An implicit purpose of the frameworks is to empower payers to negotiate value-based pricing of drugs. Although the impulse to measure value in economic terms is desirable, the threshold for defining value should include all stakeholders, including patients. In line with regulatory agencies, these frameworks prioritize aspects of efficacy, whereas QoL is underrepresented or even missing. A detailed comparison of these frameworks shows inconsistent approaches with respect to QoL. Although the ICER Value Assessment Framework, ESMO scales, and ASCO-VF consider QoL data by adjusting the score, QoL domain is not evaluated by the MSKCC Drug Abacus or the NCCN Evidence Blocks. There is heterogeneity among frameworks, even among those that do address the patient experience. ASCO-VF includes only two aspects of QoL: palliation of symptoms and treatment-free interval. The ESMO-MCBS emphasis on QoL data is broader and even includes a separate scale for QoL studies. QoL adjustments for studies evaluating OS, PFS, or objective response rate allow upgrading of the score if patients have improved QoL. However, for drugs approved based on a PFS improvement, the scale downgrades the score if the drug leads to improved PFS without showing an improvement in QoL, but for trials whose efficacy is assessed using PFS alone, if QoL data are not reported, there is, paradoxically, no penalty. Notably, the ICER Value Assessment Framework evaluates the quality-adjusted life year and other patient-related metrics, such as early return to work. Although a very important addition to the armamentarium for quantifying the value of new drugs, these frameworks have limitations. Most of these frameworks depend on RCTs, grading each experimental drug versus a specific control group (which may not be an established standard of care). Although RCTs are considered the gold standard of clinical evidence, single-arm trials are increasingly supporting drug approvals. This results in difficulty in grading the value of many drugs. Additionally, approaches to the inclusion of QoL data are inconsistent and do not encourage the reporting, in full, of QoL data. These scales can also attempt to incorporate the patients' perspective (through PROs) in a more robust manner. Finally, adjustment of the score using

real-world data and information on low-grade (and not just high-grade) toxicities may result in frameworks that are more relevant to the end users of cancer drugs.

EXPEDITED PROGRAMS AND ONCOLOGY DRUG APPROVALS IN THE UNITED STATES AND EUROPE

Over the past decade, the FDA and the EMA have developed programs designed to expedite the development and regulatory review of new drugs. Across jurisdictions, these expedited programs share a common goal of bringing “important medications to the market as quickly as possible” for serious and life-threatening diseases. Understanding the implications of these expedited programs is important for oncologists and patients, particularly given the rapid expansion of these programs. For example, in 2018, 73% (43 of 59) of new drugs approved by the FDA were granted at least one expedited program; by contrast, 34% of new drugs received expedited approval in 2000. Here, we review the key expedited approval programs used by the FDA and the EMA and their application to oncology drug approvals.

Which Expedited Programs for Cancer Are Available in the United States and Europe?

Expediting regulatory review

After sponsors conduct clinical trials, the FDA and EMA will ordinarily review the new drug application or original biologics license application (FDA) or the marketing authorization application (EMA), which includes all of the evidence generated on the drug’s safety and efficacy for its intended use. The FDA and the EMA have expedited programs specifically to accelerate this regulatory review period. In the United States, the priority review program, which was codified in 1992, leads to FDA review in 6 months (compared with 10 months for standard review). To qualify for priority review, a new drug or new indication must treat a serious condition and provide a “significant improvement in safety or effectiveness.” In its guidance for industry, the FDA explains that “significant improvement” may include evidence of increased effectiveness, substantial reduction of a treatment-limiting adverse reaction, or evidence of safety and effectiveness in a new patient population. The EMA has an analogous program, known as an “accelerated assessment” procedure, to shorten the regulatory review period. For drugs of a “major interest for public health and in particular from the viewpoint of therapeutic innovation,” the EMA would reduce its assessment time for a new marketing authorization application to 150 days (compared with 210 days for standard review).

In practice, most new drugs receive priority review by the FDA, whereas accelerated assessment by the EMA is relatively less common. Overall, in 2018, 43 (73%) new drug approvals received priority review by the FDA, compared with only four (10%) new drugs granted accelerated assessment by the EMA. Among cancer drugs approved by the FDA and the EMA between 2007 and 2017, approximately 61% received priority review by the FDA, compared with 22% that received accelerated assessment by the EMA. For example, although nivolumab and pembrolizumab received priority review for their initial approvals by the FDA in advanced melanoma, only nivolumab received accelerated assessment by the EMA.

Finally, the FDA recently announced a pilot program, referred to as Real Time Oncology Review, to further streamline the regulatory review process. In this pilot program, the FDA can begin reviewing clinical trial results once the trial database is locked and before these data are formally submitted to the FDA. The pilot program is limited to new indications for already approved drugs; further, to qualify, drugs should be likely to demonstrate substantial improvements over available therapy and have straightforward trial designs and endpoints (e.g., OS in a RCT). In 2018, the FDA approved the first drug (ribociclib in combination with fulvestrant for the treatment of postmenopausal women with hormone receptor–positive HER2-negative advanced or metastatic breast cancer) through this pilot program. The FDA reported that the approval was less than 1 month after the sponsor's submission date.^[75]

Expediting drug development

Although priority review and accelerated assessment can shorten the regulatory review period, these programs do not measurably affect clinical development times, defined as the time elapsed during clinical trials, which typically advance from small phase I studies to larger phase II and phase III safety and efficacy studies. The FDA and EMA have separate programs specifically intended to reduce the duration of the clinical development period: fast track and breakthrough therapy designation by the FDA and the priority medicines scheme (PRIME) by the EMA. These expedited programs may be combined with approval pathways that permit surrogate endpoints: the FDA's accelerated approval and the EMA's conditional marketing authorization.

Accelerated approval and conditional marketing authorization allow FDA or EMA approval, respectively, on the basis of less comprehensive clinical data than standard approval. Specifically, the FDA permits accelerated approval to be based on a surrogate or intermediate endpoint that is “reasonably likely to predict clinical benefit.” The FDA expects that drugs

granted accelerated approval will generally provide a “meaningful advance” over available therapies. For conditional marketing authorization, the EMA requires that a drug demonstrate a positive risk-benefit balance, show that benefits of immediate availability outweigh the risks based on the result of additional data still being required, and fulfill an unmet medical need. In exchange for earlier approval, the FDA and EMA require that sponsors complete confirmatory or “postapproval” trials within an agreed-upon timeframe to provide more comprehensive data after approval. A difference between the two jurisdictions is that the conditional marketing authorization is only valid for 1 year on a renewable basis provided that the benefit-risk balance remains positive, whereas FDA’s accelerated approval is not time limited. Cancer drugs are frequently granted accelerated approval or conditional marketing authorization. One study found that cancer indications accounted for 79% (19 of 24) of accelerated approvals granted by the FDA from 2009 to 2013. Similarly, cancer drugs accounted for 57% (17 of 30) of the conditional marketing authorizations granted by the EMA from 2006 to 2016.

Finally, the FDA’s fast track and breakthrough therapy programs are designed to make the clinical testing period broadly more efficient. Fast track designation is reserved for drugs intended to treat a serious condition and for which “nonclinical and clinical data demonstrate the potential to address an unmet need.” Sponsors of fast track–designated drugs have opportunities for more frequent interactions with FDA reviewers to discuss study design, extent of safety data required to support approval, dose-response concerns, use of biomarkers, and other issues. Fast track designation can also permit rolling review of the marketing application before the sponsor submits the complete application. In 2012, the U.S. Congress established the breakthrough therapy program in response to concerns that “major breakthroughs in drugs and other treatments for debilitating and terminal diseases...[were] not always getting to patients though the most efficient and safe pathways.” To qualify for the breakthrough therapy designation, a new drug must be intended to treat a serious or life-threatening disease and demonstrate substantial improvement on a clinically significant endpoint over available therapies. Sponsors of breakthrough-designated products receive the benefits of fast track designation, as well as intensive guidance from FDA reviewers and senior managers to reduce overall trial durations and ensure efficient drug development.

Parallel to the FDA’s breakthrough therapy program, the EMA launched the PRIME scheme in 2016 to offer early dialogue on development plans and evidence requirements for approval.

Products in the PRIME program can also benefit from scientific advice by additional stakeholders, including health technology assessment bodies, to facilitate faster access by patients after approval. To be eligible for the PRIME program, a drug must “offer a major therapeutic advantage over existing treatments or benefit patients without treatment options” on the basis of early clinical data. Early experience with the breakthrough therapy and PRIME programs indicates that they are increasingly being used by cancer medicines. For example, cancer drugs represent approximately 56% of all breakthrough-designated medicines approved since the program’s creation. Similarly, as of January 31, 2019, the EMA has received 214 PRIME eligibility requests. Oncology accounted for the most requests overall and for a plurality of successfully granted PRIME status (13 requests [23%]).

Orphan drug development

In addition to the formal expedited programs reviewed herein, cancer drugs may benefit from other regulatory programs and incentives. Notably, in the FDA's and EMA's jurisdictions, sponsors can apply for orphan drug designation for drugs intended to treat rare diseases. Although not an expedited program per se, orphan drug designation can benefit from increased market exclusivity, protocol assistance, and fee reductions; additionally, in the United States, sponsors of orphan drugs can receive tax credits for clinical trial costs. By the end of 2016, 128 drugs have been approved with orphan designation by the EMA, with more than 40% in the area of oncology.

What Are the Benefits and Risks of Expedited Approvals?

As a result of these expedited approval programs, the FDA and EMA are among the fastest drug-regulatory agencies globally, and the majority of new cancer drug approvals benefit from at least one expedited program. Development times for drugs receiving fast track or breakthrough therapy designation are significantly shorter than those for nonexpedited drugs. Specifically, breakthrough therapy drugs were associated with a median development time of 4.8 years, from the start of clinical testing to approval, compared with the 8 or 10 years commonly associated with the drug-development process. For example, pembrolizumab was first approved by the FDA for advanced melanoma in 2014 and by the EMA in 2015, only 3 to 4 years after the start of its first-in-human clinical trial.

Physicians and patients must balance the benefits of early access with the increased uncertainty around the safety and efficacy of expedited drugs. This uncertainty may not be clearly communicated to the public. For example, in a randomized national survey of board-

certified internists and specialists in the United States, 77% of respondents believed that there was high-quality evidence that a drug is more effective than existing treatments if it was designated as a breakthrough by the FDA, and 94% preferred a hypothetical cancer drug described as a “breakthrough” over an equally effective alternative without that descriptor. However, one study found no evidence that breakthrough-designated drugs provide significant improvements in safety or efficacy compared with nonbreakthrough-designated drugs. Some expedited drugs may fail to confirm clinical benefit in postapproval studies. For example, atezolizumab was approved by the FDA in 2016 with breakthrough designation and accelerated approval for patients with advanced urothelial carcinoma, but it did not significantly improve OS in a recent phase III confirmatory study (IMvigor211) compared with chemotherapy (11.1 vs. 10.6 months; hazard ratio, 0.87; 95% CI, 0.63–1.21). In addition, several studies have reported that accelerated approval, priority review, and fast track drugs are associated with an increased risk for safety-related issues.

How Good Is Patient Participation in Cancer Clinical Trials?

Despite the importance of cancer clinical trials, the proportion of all patients enrolled in studies is low. Only 3% of patients with cancer in the United States participate in trials. Moreover, approximately 40% of all trials (and approximately 60% of phase III trials) fail to achieve minimum patient enrollment. These low participation rates are not simply a reflection of patients not wanting to participate in studies; they are primarily driven by study design and health system barriers to participation. Survey data suggest that 85% of Americans believe that trials must be discussed as a standard-of-care option, and 74% were willing to participate if asked by someone they trust. However, only 41% of cancer survivors surveyed recalled having a discussion about clinical trials with their health care team.

Why Do Patients Participate in Clinical Trials?

Most patients cite altruistic reasons, such as advancing science and helping to find treatments to save other lives, as the most important factors for trial participation; the chance to improve their own disease condition is listed as the third reason. Another study highlighted access to best treatment and contributing to science as the main reasons for patients choosing to participate in research studies.

Patient expectation of clinical trials is a major challenge in contemporary oncology. A clinical trial, by definition, is conducted because there is uncertainty about the benefits from a certain intervention. Early-phase clinical trials, such as phase I and II trials, are conducted to

elicit the appropriate dose and safety of the new drug and to assess whether the drug has responses good enough to be tested in a phase III trial. Thus, the expectation of clinical benefits for participants themselves, especially from early-phase trials, is low. However, one study reported that more than 80% of patients enrolled in early-phase clinical oncology trials were motivated by the potential of a clinical benefit, with approximately half expecting tumor shrinkage and approximately one-tenth anticipating a cure. Unfortunately, this misconception is even fueled by some physicians, who mistakenly assume that the modern biomarker-based cancer drug trials could have therapeutic value, even during the phase I stage, a conclusion reached by focusing solely on success stories and ignoring the failures. This false optimism of achieving therapeutic benefit from participating in phase I trials will lead to disappointment and perpetuate negativity toward trial participation in the community of patients, their families, and friends.

Phase III RCTs are conducted when there is equipoise between two treatment options; however, randomization can be a tricky concept for patients to understand. Even among patients with advanced cancer participating in a radiotherapy trial, the majority did not understand that cure was not possible. Another study has shown that expectations from trials were unrealistic, even among physicians.

LITRATURE REVIEW

Vreman et al.,(2022) Background: The European Medicines Agency (EMA) aims to resolve uncertainties associated with conditionally approved drugs by imposing post-approval studies. Results from these studies may be relevant for health technology assessment (HTA) organizations. This study investigated the role of regulator-imposed post-approval studies within HTA. Methods: For all conditionally approved drugs up to December 2018, regulator-imposed post-approval studies were identified from EMA's public assessment reports. The availability for and inclusion of study results in relative effectiveness (re)assessments were analyzed for 4 European HTA organizations: NICE (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, England/Wales), HAS (Haute Autorité de Santé, France), ZIN (Zorginstituut Nederland, the Netherlands) and the European Network for Health Technology Assessment (EUnetHTA, Europe). When study results became available between an HTA organization's initial assessment and reassessment, it was evaluated whether and how they affected the assessment and its outcome. Results: For 36 conditionally approved drugs, 98 post-approval studies were imposed. In total, 81 initial relative effectiveness assessments (REAs) and 13

reassessments were available, with numbers of drugs (re)assessed varying greatly between jurisdictions. Study results were available for 16 initial REAs (20%) and included in 14 (88%), and available for 10 reassessments (77%) and included in all (100%). Five reassessments had an outcome different from the initial REA, with 4 (2 positive and 2 negative changes) relating directly to the new study results. Reassessments often cited the inability of post-approval studies to resolve the concerns reported in the initial REA. Conclusion: Results from regulator-imposed post-approval studies for conditionally approved drugs were not often used in REAs by HTA organizations, because they were often not yet available at the time of initial assessment and because reassessments were scarce. When available, results from post-approval studies were almost always used within HTA, and they have led to changes in conclusions about drugs' relative effectiveness. Post-approval studies can be relevant within HTA but the current lack of alignment between regulators and HTA organizations limits their potential. Keywords: Conditional, Authorization, Health Technology Assessment, Post-approval, Relative Effectiveness, Evidence.^[58]

Meilan K Han et al.,(2020) Introduction: Quercetin is a plant flavonoid and has potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. In a preclinical model of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), quercetin reduced markers of both oxidative stress and lung inflammation and also reduced rhinovirus-induced progression of lung disease. Although quercetin appears to be an attractive natural alternative to manage COPD, the safety of quercetin supplementation in this population is unknown. Methods:We recruited COPD patients with mild-to-severe lung disease with FVE1 ranging between >35% and <80% and supplemented with either placebo or quercetin at 500, 1000 or 2000 mg/day in a dose-escalation manner. The duration of quercetin supplementation was 1 week. Results:Patients had no study drug-related severe adverse events based on blood tests, which included both complete blood counts and evaluation of comprehensive metabolic panel. One of the patients reported mild adverse events included gastro-oesophageal reflux disease, which was observed in both placebo and quercetin groups. Conclusions:Quercetin was safely tolerated up to 2000 mg/day as assessed by lung function, blood profile and COPD assessment test questionnaire.^[59]

Elodie Baumfeld Andre et al., (2020) Purpose: There is a need to develop hybrid trial methodology combining the bestparts of traditional randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and observational studydesigns to produce real-world evidence (RWE) that provides adequate

scientific evidence for regulatory decision-making. Methods: This review explores how hybrid study designs that include features of RCTs and studies with real-world data (RWD) can combine the advantages of both to generate RWE that is fit for regulatory purposes. Results: Some hybrid designs include randomization and use pragmatic outcomes; other designs use single-arm trial data supplemented with external comparators derived from RWD or leverage novel data collection approaches to capture long-term outcomes in a real-world setting. Some of these approaches have already been successfully used in regulatory decisions, raising the possibility that studies using RWD could increasingly be used to augment or replace traditional RCTs for the demonstration of drug effectiveness in certain contexts. These changes come against a background of long reliance on RCTs for regulatory decision-making, which are labor-intensive, costly, and produce data that can have limited applicability in real-world clinical practice. Conclusions: While RWE from observational studies is well accepted for satisfying postapproval safety monitoring requirements, it has not commonly been used to demonstrate drug effectiveness for regulatory purposes. However, this position is changing as regulatory opinions, guidance frameworks, and RWD methodologies are evolving, with growing recognition of the value of using RWE that is acceptable for regulatory decision-making.^[60]

Rajesh R Tampi et al.,(2021) Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most common cause for dementia worldwide. Until recently, all approved treatments for AD were symptomatic and not disease modifying. On 7 June 2021, the US FDA approved aducanumab, a human IgG1 anti-A β monoclonal antibody selective for A β aggregates, as the first disease-modifying treatment for AD. Aducanumab is approved in the United States for the treatment of mild cognitive impairment or mild-dementia stage of AD. In this Editorial, we review the trial data for aducanumab in the treatment of AD and the controversies that its approval has generated.^[61]

Cabral de Guimaraes TA, et al.,(2021) Age-related macular degeneration (AMD) is the leading cause of irreversible blindness in the developed world. The identification of the central role of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) in the pathogenesis of neovascular AMD and the introduction of anti-VEGF agents as gold-standard treatment, have drastically changed its prognosis—something yet to be seen in dry AMD. Several therapeutic avenues with a wide variability of targets are currently being investigated in dry AMD. The approaches being investigated to reduce the rate of disease progression include, (1) drugs

with antioxidative properties, (2) inhibitors of the complement cascade, (3) neuroprotective agents, (4) visual cycle inhibitors, (5) gene therapy and (6) cell-based therapies. A number of early phase clinical trials have provided promising results, with many more ongoing and anticipated in the near future. In this review, we aim to provide an update of the interventional trials to date and future prospects for the treatment of dry AMD.^[62]

David P. Nichols et al.,(2021) Rationale: The cystic fibrosis (CF) modulator drug, elexacaftor/tezacaftor/ivacaftor (ETI), proved highly effective in controlled clinical trials for individuals with at least one F508del allele, which occurs in at least 85% of people with CF. Objectives: PROMISE is a post approval study to understand the broad effects of ETI through 30 months' clinical use in a more diverse U.S. patient population with planned analyses after 6 months. Methods: Prospective, observational study in 487 people with CF age 12 years or older with at least one F508del allele starting ETI for the first time. Assessments occurred before and 1, 3, and 6 months into ETI therapy. Outcomes included change in percent predicted FEV1 (ppFEV1), sweat chloride concentration, body mass index (BMI), and self-reported respiratory symptoms. Measurements and Main Results: Average age was 25.1 years, and 44.1% entered the study using tezacaftor/ivacaftor or lumacaftor/ivacaftor, whereas 6.7% were using ivacaftor, consistent with F508del homozygosity and G551D allele, respectively. At 6 months into ETI therapy, ppFEV1 improved 9.76 percentage points (95% confidence interval [CI], 8.76 to 10.76) from baseline, cystic fibrosis questionnaire-revised respiratory domain score improved 20.4 points (95% CI, 18.3 to 22.5), and sweat chloride decreased 241.7 mmol/L (95% CI, 243.8 to 239.6). BMI also significantly increased. Changes were larger in those naive to modulators but substantial in all groups, including those treated with ivacaftor at baseline. Conclusions: ETI by clinical prescription provided large improvements in lung function, respiratory symptoms, and BMI in a diverse population naive to modulator drug therapy, using existing two-drug combinations, or using ivacaftor alone. Each group also experienced significant reductions in sweat chloride concentration, which correlated with improved ppFEV1 in the overall study population.^[63]

T. Bieber et al.,(2021) Background Janus kinase (JAK) inhibition is a new mode of action in atopic dermatitis (AD); clarity about drug class safety considerations in the context of AD is important. Baricitinib, an oral, reversible, selective inhibitor of JAK1/JAK2, is in late-stage development for adult patients with moderate-to-severe AD. Objective To report pooled safety

data for baricitinib in patients with moderate-to-severe AD in the clinical development program including long-term extension (LTE) studies. **Methods** This analysis included patient-level safety data from six double-blinded, randomized, placebo-controlled studies (one phase 2 and five phase 3), one double-blinded, randomized, LTE study and one open-label LTE study, reported in three data sets: placebo-controlled, 2-mg–4-mg extended and All-bari AD. Safety outcomes include treatment-emergent adverse events, adverse events of special interest and abnormal laboratory changes. Proportions of patients with events and incidence rates were calculated. **Results** Data were collected for 2531 patients who were given baricitinib for 2247 patient-years (median duration 310 days). The frequency of serious infections, opportunistic infections and conjunctival disorders was low and similar between treatment groups in the placebo-controlled period. The most common serious infections were eczema herpeticum [n=11, incidence rates (IR)=0.5], cellulitis (n=6, IR=0.3) and pneumonia (n=3, IR=0.1). There were four opportunistic infections (IR=0.2). No malignancies, gastrointestinal perforations, positively adjudicated cardiovascular events or tuberculosis were reported in the placebo-controlled period in baricitinib-treated patients. Frequency of herpes simplex was higher in the 4-mg group (6.1%) vs. the 2-mg (3.6%) and placebo group (2.7%); IRs in the extended dataset (2-mg IR=9.6; 4-mg IR=14.5) were lower vs. the placebo-controlled data set (2-mg IR=12.4; 4-mg IR=21.3). In the All-bari AD data set, there were two positively adjudicated major adverse cardiovascular events (2-mg group): two venous thrombosis events (4-mg group) and one death. **Conclusion** This integrated safety analysis in patients with moderate-to-severe AD confirms the established safety profile of baricitinib.^[64]

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

To enable timely access to innovative drugs, the European Medicines Agency (EMA) can conditionally approve drugs based on a less comprehensive evidence package when immediate availability of the drug outweighs the risks due to the less comprehensive evidence package. Importantly, the benefit-risk balance still needs to be judged positive, but more uncertainty may be considered acceptable in light of the drug's potential to address unmet medical needs.

DISCUSSION

We conducted a prospective, multi centre, open-labeled, randomized superiority clinical trial and hypothesized that Favipiravir would be superior to Arbidol in terms of efficacy for

moderate symptoms, and would accelerate the clinical recovery of pyrexia, cough, and breathing difficulties compared with Arbidol.

Favipiravir treatment did not improve clinical recovery rate of Day 7 (61.21%) compared to Arbidol group (51.67%). However, it did significantly improve the latency to cough relief and decreased the duration of pyrexia. Favipiravir was not associated with any differences in ICU admission, AOT/NMV, dyspnea, respiratory failure or all-cause mortality.

Interestingly, post-hoc observation showed that a trend of Favipiravir being effective to improve clinical recovery rate at Day 7 in moderate COVID-19 patients compared to Arbidol. This effect diminished for severe/critical COVID-19 patients. Additionally, post-hoc analysis showed that for moderate COVID-19 patients, Favipiravir was associated with decreased auxiliary oxygen therapy or noninvasive mechanical ventilation rate with marginal significance ($P=0.0541$). Finally, in the FAS, post-hoc analysis also showed that Favipiravir treatment significantly decreased de novo incidences of dyspnea. Whether Favipiravir would be only effective for moderate COVID-19 patients, or could Favipiravir be used to prevent disease progression, is a question warrant future investigation.

The combination of traditional Chinese medicine and antiviral drugs is more common in China, which is due to the traditional medical culture background of the treatment of choice. Also, anti-infection and immune regulation play an important role in the treatment of the COVID-19. Ancillary treatments, such as traditional Chinese medicine, anti-infection and immune modulatory drugs, were without statistical difference between groups.

Our trial has several limitations. Firstly, for COVID-19, there is no clinically proven effective antiviral drug to serve as the control arm. Although Chinese guideline had recommended several options including Arbidol, no RCT results on these drugs were reported. Arbidol was widely used by Chinese doctors in the beginning stage of this epidemic of COVID-19 (Jan. 1-30, 2020) based on in vitro evidence.¹² For ethical reasons, we chose Arbidol for the control arm. Secondly, observation time frame was limited due to the urgency of this epidemic. For the same reason, no relapse (including nucleic acid conversion, pyrexia, cough, or pneumonia progress by radiology) tracking were performed for the discharged patients. Thirdly, in the inclusion criteria, we did not force positive nucleic acid test as a necessity. The accuracy of nucleic acid assay was limited, which might due to multiple reasons including previous treatment, latency of onset, sampling method, biological specimen characteristics. This

particular accuracy problem was a known issue among clinical practitioners across the world. It was estimated that the assay might have at most 30%-50% of sensitivity for patients in early stage of the disease, whilst contact history, clinical manifestations, radiology evidences, and lab results including leukopenia and lymphopenia could be confirmatory for these nucleic-acid-negative pneumonia patients. In the Chinese guideline, patients meeting these criteria were considered as with clinically confirmed COVID-19. In this trial, 46.55% patients in Favipiravir group and 38.33% in Arbidol group were nucleic-acid-positive at enrollment. Considering the population incidence of COVID-19 infection at the time of this trial in Wuhan, we consider the probability for mis-identifying patients of pneumonia disease other than COVID-19 into this trial is low. Fourthly, the protocol does not prespecify clinical classification as a stratification factor. Ethical concerns arose against completely excluding severe/critical cases from potential beneficial treatment. Additionally, because of the complexity of the disease, progression from moderate to severe/critical is possible. Terminating trial treatment to such patients from the study was considered unacceptable. Post-hoc analysis showed that both treatment and clinical classification contributed significantly to the primary outcome of clinical recovery rate at Day 7. Difference of the frequency of severe/critical patients between groups reached a marginal significance, which made an important impact on the trial outcome.

Previous studies have demonstrated more favourable renal biomarker profiles in TAF-containing regimens compared with TDF-containing regimens; however, the sample sizes of individual trials and the overall low rate of clinically significant renal adverse events in these trials limited the ability to detect differences in the rates of these events with the exception of the pooled pivotal EVG trials. In the present analysis, we integrated data from 26 individual trials and were able to demonstrate the renal safety of TAF over TDF across a broad range of PLH, including those who were treatment naive and those who were virologically suppressed at switch. After 12519 person-years of exposure to TAF, there were no cases of PRT or Fanconi syndrome (identified objectively and independently by the primary investigator caring for the participant) and significantly fewer discontinuations due to renal adverse events in the TAF group compared with the TDF group. Notably, only three (0.02%) renal discontinuation events were reported in participants on TAF; none of these were reported as study drug-related by the investigators, and all had plausible alternative causes.

In treatment-naive participants, we observed fewer overall renal adverse events in participants taking TAF-containing regimens compared with those taking TDF-containing regimens. No difference in overall renal adverse events was observed in participants enrolled in switch studies; this may be explained by the fact that participants in those studies were already maintained on TDF at the time of enrolment, and thus self-selected as less likely to develop renal adverse events.

By using an integrated analysis, we were able to demonstrate favourable changes in renal biomarkers in participants taking TAF-containing regimens compared with those taking TDF, both in treatment-naive and treatment-experienced patients who switched to TAF-containing regimens. Our findings demonstrate favourable changes in CrCl as well as in proximal tubule function (RBP and β 2M ratios). We also observed a lower incidence of treatment-emergent proteinuria in participants taking TAF-containing regimens. The observed incidences of proteinuria were high, but notably these are cumulative incidences over 96 weeks of follow-up, and are consistent with previously reported incidences of proteinuria in PLH. These biomarker findings in combination with the clinical outcomes suggest that TAF does not induce proximal tubule dysfunction.

The mechanism for the improved renal safety profile of TAF is likely related to the approximately 90% lower plasma levels of TFV seen in participants receiving TAF compared with those receiving TDF. This mechanism is supported by the reported association between declines in renal tubular function and higher TFV plasma concentrations.

Conversely, the use of boosting agents such as RTV and COBI increase TFV exposure, and accordingly the use of boosting agents has been associated with an increased risk of renal adverse events. A recent meta-analysis sought to compare the renal safety profiles of TDF-containing regimens in the presence and absence of boosting agents, and suggested that unboosted TDF could have a similar renal safety profile as TAF. However, the aforementioned meta-analysis is limited by a relatively small number of participants and short duration of follow-up. In the findings presented here, nine out of 10 PRT cases occurred in participants receiving boosted regimens; however, one severe case of PRT occurred in a participant receiving TDF without a boosting agent. Our data support the principle that boosting agents increase the risk of TFV-associated renal adverse events; however, our ability to make robust conclusions about the renal safety of unboosted TDF is limited by the comparatively small number of participants taking such regimens (of 9322 total participants,

2962 were on TDF, and of those 1101 were on TDF without a boosting agent). Although the question of renal safety of TDF in unboosted regimens warrants more evaluation, the available data indicate that TAF can be safely used with boosted as well as unboosted third agents with a very low incidence of clinically significant renal events.

We note several limitations to our analyses. It is challenging to diagnose PRT, and no commonly accepted single diagnostic exists in the clinic to confirm PRT. As such, we utilized investigator-reported events to document PRT, which may have underestimated the number of PRT cases. A reporting bias is possible given the use of investigator reported events, but is unlikely to have affected our findings as most of the included trials were double-blinded, and the majority of reported renal discontinuation events and PRT cases were reported during blinded trial phases. Our clinical trial participants may have been healthier than the general population of PLH due to the presence of inclusion and exclusion criteria in the trials, although TAF was found to safe in patients with impaired renal function (CrCl 30–70ml/min, many of whom with diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and proteinuria), with no reported cases of PRT and overall stable renal function through 96 weeks of follow-up. We also acknowledge that we did not have individual level data on the duration of prior TDF therapy in our trials and therefore could not adjust the rates accordingly.

Despite these limitations, the integrated analysis presented here is based on the large cumulative exposure in person-years to TAF, both in antiretroviral naïve and virally suppressed populations. Furthermore, the pooled data used for analysis includes a demographically diverse population with a wide age range, a large number of women, and diverse ethnic background. It is also notable that a proportion of participants had relatively low CrCl, with variable CrCl eligibility cut-offs of 30, 50, or 70ml/min in the trials included in this analysis. The clinical trial data are supported by experience from the post approval use in PLH in which currently there has been no renal safety signal with 1.1 million cumulative person-years exposure to TAF.

In conclusion, the pooled data from clinical studies, representing over 12500 patient-years of follow-up in children and adults on TAF, suggests that the favourable renal biomarker profile observed with TAF vs. TDF in the individual trials translates into a lower rate of clinically significant renal events. These data support a comparative renal safety advantage of TAF over TDF in a broad range of PLH.

In this study of US-based clinical trials with human participants that were published in high-impact journals in 2017, only 15% of the trials could have been feasibly pursued using currently available realworld data from structured EHRs and insurance claims. In particular, replication of the trials of FDA-regulated pharmaceutical interventions was often precluded by the lack of FDA approval at the time of trial publication. Regardless, our estimate was likely a best-case estimate; additional work would be needed to ultimately establish the reliability of observational data sources to generate RWE that could be sufficiently consistent with the trial's intent. Because most trials published in the highest-impact journals were of new drugs that had not yet been approved by the FDA, the findings may reflect that these journals are more likely to publish the pivotal trials that support a new FDA approval.

However, the findings also reinforce the caution about the promise of RWE replacing RCTs. Using observational methods and data sources is not feasible for examining the safety and efficacy of a medical product that is not in widespread use in routine clinical practice.

This study also raises a second caution about the promise of RWE augmenting RCTs. Many of the trials could not be replicated because they would require data that are unlikely to appear in an EHR in structured form if at all. Several improvements in the collection and analysis of EHR data may enhance the use of real-world data to generate RWE, including increased use of patient-reported outcomes as part of routine clinical care, more widespread use of medical device surveillance initiatives, and improvements in natural language processing for free text in EHRs.

The pharmaceutical industry spent \$22.4 billion on phase 3 and phase 4 clinical trials in 2011,¹⁶ and the total cost of research and development for a single drug has been estimated at \$2.9 billion.¹⁷ Thus, the theoretical potential for financial savings through RWE-based medical product evaluations is substantial. Furthermore, the evidentiary gaps and unanswered clinical questions that exist are unlikely to be pursued through clinical trials, but for which RWE may offer critical insights. For instance, RWE could be generated as post approval evidence of medical product safety and efficacy for drugs with limited evidence to support their use.¹⁸ Similarly, producing sufficient evidence to support an FDA action to communicate a safety concern to patients and clinicians can take more than 4 years.¹⁹ Real-world evidence can be used to more rapidly generate actionable safety evidence, which is rarely pursued through clinical trials. Furthermore, RWE may be particularly useful because

prospective post approval studies can be difficult to recruit for given that patients can receive the therapy outside the trial, as occurred with the off-label use of atrial septal closure devices. The FDA continues to invest in its ability to use RWE. As part of the President's Budget for fiscal year 2019, the FDA developed a \$100 million proposal to build a medical data enterprise system using EHR data from about 10 million people to build a foundation for more robust postmarketing studies. This investment represents an evolution for the FDA from primarily relying on insurance claims for postmarketing research to using EHR data, which are a richer source of real-world clinical data and have a shorter reporting lag time than claims data. The proposal also aims to address the lack of standardization of structured EHR data and of interoperability between different systems. In addition, the RWE program of the FDA will develop a framework for evaluating studies that use RWE in terms of the reliability of real-world data sources and the ability of study designs and conducts to meet regulatory requirements. These initiatives could present uses for real-world data that may not have been considered otherwise.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, the results are limited to a subset of all clinical trials published in 1 year, although we suspect that these trials represent those that have great implications for clinical practice and that are relevant to clinical practice guidelines and regulators. Second, in establishing whether an intervention could be ascertained from real-world data, we assumed that a pivotal trial for a new indication of a previously FDA-approved drug was replicable because it could theoretically be used off-label, although we did not confirm how common this practice was for each drug and indication. Third, in the analysis of study inclusion and exclusion criteria, we included trials if 80% of the individual criteria were considered as able to be ascertained from structured EHR or claims data, but we did not consider the relative importance or quality of each criterion. Fourth, we considered only primary end points mentioned in the article abstract and thus did not consider all measured study end points, limiting the generalizability of our findings. Fifth, we assumed that an EHR or claims diagnosis would be equivalent to a diagnosis in a clinical trial, which may not always be true given that clinical trials often follow stricter guidelines for diagnosis. For example, in a clinical trial, a diagnosis of myocardial infarction may require specific symptoms and troponin-level patterns, which were not evaluated for feasibility to be ascertained unless they were explicitly stated in the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

In addition, the definition of the feasibility of a trial's characteristics to be ascertained from observational data does not consider whether an observational database would have a sufficient sample with which to perform an analysis (eg, a newly marketed drug or drug for a rare disease) or whether a financial incentive exists to use observational data to replicate a particular clinical trial. Thus, a trial that we identified to be replicable with real-world data may be only suitable to assess sample size feasibility within a given observational data source and then may be found not to be sufficiently powered or feasible to replicate. In addition, the determination of replicability inherently involved an element of subjectivity and did not consider natural language processing as a mechanism for extracting and analyzing real-world data. Although this method has been used in single-center studies, to our knowledge, it is not yet widely applied across health systems for the purpose of generating RWE. As methods become more advanced, opportunities to generate RWE and thereby use RWE to replicate trials will increase.

This study did not consider that the clinical settings in which real-world data are collected are often not the same as the environments in which RCTs are conducted. For instance, patient age, sex, race/ethnicity, or socioeconomic background; clinician location (eg, tertiary center vs private practice); or practice volume are likely to vary between the 2 settings. Nevertheless, this difference is one potential advantage of real-world data because the populations studied are more likely to be representative of the broader population of patients with disease.

In COLCOT, the risk of the primary composite efficacy end point of death from cardiovascular causes, resuscitated cardiac arrest, myocardial infarction, stroke, or urgent hospitalization for angina leading to coronary revascularization, as assessed in a time-to-event analysis, was significantly lower among the patients who were randomly assigned to receive 0.5 mg of colchicine once daily than among those who received placebo. This result was due predominantly to a lower incidence of strokes and urgent hospitalizations for angina leading to coronary revascularization.

These results were observed against a background of appropriate medications, which included aspirin, a different antiplatelet agent, and a statin in 98 to 99% of the patients. In addition, percutaneous coronary intervention was performed in 93% of the patients for their index myocardial infarction. The benefits of colchicine with regard to cardiovascular end points in COLCOT were at least as large as those of canakinumab in CANTOS.² In the small

subgroup of patients with available data, as expected, a large (>65%) reduction in the C-reactive protein level occurred over the first 6 months after myocardial infarction in both trial groups in COLCOT, but the difference between the changes in the groups was not significant. These findings must be interpreted cautiously given that this was a small subgroup that was not randomly selected from the full trial sample. A similar observation was made with white-cell counts. The different patient populations involved in the two trials — early after myocardial infarction in COLCOT and stable coronary disease in CANTOS — may also have affected the relationship between biomarkers of inflammation and the effects of treatments on ischemic end points.

The known benefits of colchicine in the treatment of pericarditis were not at play in COLCOT. Postinfarction pericarditis typically occurs within the first few days after the injury, whereas the mean time from the index myocardial infarction to randomization was 13.5 days. There were only two patients with a first positively adjudicated event of urgent hospitalization for angina leading to coronary revascularization within 14 days after randomization, and the median time to this clinical end point was 258 days.

The most common adverse events observed were gastrointestinal. Diarrhea was reported in 9.7% of the patients in the colchicine group and in 8.9% of those in the placebo group, and nausea occurred in 1.8% and 1.0%, respectively. Infection as a serious adverse event was more frequent in the colchicine group than in the placebo group (in 2.2% vs. 1.6% of the patients), and pneumonia as a serious adverse event was also more frequent in the colchicine group (0.9% vs. 0.4%). These differences in the incidence of infections could be due to the play of chance or could reflect altered immunologic responses. In contrast to canakinumab, colchicine did not increase the incidence of septic shock in our trial. Infections have previously been described in patients who have attempted suicide by taking an overdose of colchicine. There was no serious adverse event of myopathy linked to colchicine despite the use of statins in 99% of the patients in the trial.

Our trial has certain limitations. The duration of follow-up was relatively short at approximately 23 months. The risks and benefits of longer-term treatment with colchicine were not evaluated. Although the inclusion of 4745 patients was sufficient for the trial to show a significant benefit with regard to the primary composite efficacy end point, a larger trial could have allowed a better assessment of individual end points and subgroups and the

risks associated with colchicine. Finally, our results apply only to patients who have recently had a myocardial infarction.

In conclusion, among patients with a recent myocardial infarction, colchicine at a dose of 0.5 mg daily led to a significantly lower percentage of patients with ischemic cardiovascular events than placebo.

THE CONTRIBUTION OF BIOLOGICALLY DERIVED PRODUCTS TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW MEDICINES

The annual global medicine market is worth about 1.1 trillion US dollars. About 35 percent of these medicines originated directly or indirectly from natural products including: plants (25%), microorganisms (13%) and animals (about 3%): natural-derived products constitute an extremely important resource for global pharmaceutical companies working on the development of new medicines. They are used as: i) a direct source of therapeutic agents, (both as pure drugs and phyto medicines); ii) a source of raw material for development of complex, semi-synthetic drugs; iii) prototypes for design of lead molecules; iv) as taxonomic markers for discovery of new drugs). About one third of the best-selling drugs in the world are natural products or their derivatives. Of the 520 new drugs approved by Food and Drug Administration (FDA) between 1983 and 1994, 39% were natural products or derived from natural products and about 60 - 80% of antibiotics and anti-cancer drugs are derived from natural products. Recently assessed the role of natural products in the drugs approved by the FDA between 1981 and 2014. They found that in this period the FDA approved 1,562 drugs, 64 (4%) were unaltered natural products, 141 (9.1%) were botanical drugs (mixture), 320 (21%) were natural product derivatives and 61 (4%) were synthetic drugs but with natural products pharmacophore.

There are many examples of globally best-selling medicines that originated from natural products – notably from higher plants, microorganism and animals. Some good examples are: i) the anti-cholesterolaemic agent's simvastatin, lovastatin, pravastatin and atorvastatin; ii) the anti-hypertensive agents: captopril and enalapril; iii) the immunosuppressive agents cyclosporin A, tacrolimus (FK506) and rapamycin; iv) the antitumoral agents taxol, docetaxel and camptothecin; v) the antibiotic and antifungal agents: penicillin, erythromycin, clarithromycin and amphotericin B.

As noted above animals are the source of about 3% of the new drugs approved by the FDA, but many important and best-selling drugs originated from animals, mainly from toxins. Captopril, an angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitor and anti-hypertensive drug was discovered by Brazilian pharmacologist in the venom of the Brazilian viper,. This is discussed in more detail in the next section. Enalapril was later developed using the same mechanism. Other examples of animal-derived drugs are exanatide, a glucagon-like peptide 1 agonist used to treat type 2 diabetes mellitus, which was originally isolated from the gila of the monster lizard, a peptide isolated from *Conus magus* which is a calcium 2.2 channel blocker used to treat neuropathic pain (for more detail about new drugs derived from animal toxins see: http://zoltantakacs.com/zt/sc/venoms_medical.shtml).

There are some clear advantages to the use of natural products in the process of drug discovery and development. They represent chemical novelties and compared with other sources they can originate lead drug candidate for complex targets. Furthermore, naturally derived constituents possess a chemical diversity unmatched by any synthetic chemical collection; they can possess bi- and tri-dimensional complex structures yet be capable of being absorbed and metabolised in the body. On the other hand, the use of naturally derived molecules as source of new medicines also presents some challenges because of the lack of specific legislation governing access to biological resources in biodiversity-rich countries. It may also be physically difficult to gain access to natural habitats and the processes necessary to isolate, purify and chemically characterise active compounds are costly and time-consuming. Most pharmaceutical companies complain about the difficulty of assaying some natural molecules in modern drug discovery programmes (high throughput screening) compared with synthetic compounds. Finally, is important to emphasise the great structural complexity of natural molecules, which makes it difficult to synthesise analogous lead compounds. Without doubt the global pharmaceutical industry has benefited greatly from biodiversity-rich countries over the last two centuries when it comes to identification of novel therapeutic targets involved in many significant chronic diseases and, particularly, the development of new drugs for the management of certain chronic diseases.

Brazil is the most biodiverse country in the world, with more than 50,000 species of higher plants (20 - 22% of the planetary total), more than 500 species of mammals, about 3,000 species of fish, more than 1,500 species of birds, more than 500 species of amphibians and

millions of species of insects and microorganisms (<http://www.sibbr.gov.br/areas/?area=biodiversidade>).

However, to date few innovative products have been developed and marketed in Brazil or abroad from active constituents derived from Brazilian biodiversity. Despite the growing number of scientific articles published internationally by Brazilian scientists on plants over the last 4 decades, we have seen that there is a negative correlation between the number of scientific papers published on Brazilian biodiversity and the number of innovative products derived from the Brazilian biome that are available on the market. I return to this topic later on in this article.

FROM THE DISCOVERY OF BRADYKININ TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF CAPTOPRIL

In 1949, **Rocha e Silva** (1910 – 1983) and **Wilson Teixeira Beraldo** (1917 – 1998), who were working at the São Paulo State Biological Institute, discovered the peptide bradykinin (BK), a hypotensive agent that stimulate smooth muscles and is released in plasma by the action of venom of the Brazilian viper, *Bothrops jararaca* or by trypsin. This discovery was first published in the first number of the journal *Ciencia e Cultura*, from the newly created Brazilian Society for the Advance of Science, which numbered Rocha amongst its founders. In the same year this discovery was published in the *American Journal of Physiology* and the article became a much-cited classic.

At the beginning of 1960s, then a young physician who had graduated from the University of São Paulo, moved to Ribeirão Preto to begin a PhD in Pharmacology under supervision of Professor **Mauricio Rocha e Silva**. Professor Rocha e Silva suggested that Sergio continue work with the venom of the Brazilian viper, *Bothrops jararaca*. Sergio subsequently discovered that the venom of *Bothrops jararaca* had a very interesting potentiating effect on the contractile action of bradykinin in the guinea pig ileum and on bradykinin-induced hypotension and he and colleagues identified the active substance responsible as bradykinin-potentiating factor (BPF). These results were published in the *British Journal of Pharmacology* in 1965. Further investigation of BPF was carried out in collaboration with many researchers from the Faculty of Medicine of Ribeiro Preto allowed to isolate and to sequence two active peptides, the pentapeptide BPP5 and the nonapeptide BPP9.

As soon as he finished his doctorate Sergio decided to spend some years as a post-doctoral researcher in London, at the Professor John Vane Laboratory in the Institute of Basic Medical Science at the Royal College of Surgeons of England. Sergio took with him to London a small sample of the purified BPF for which he and his collaborators had already determined the amino acid sequence and suggested that this venom-derived peptide inhibited the enzyme that degrades BK, which was later recognised to be the enzyme that transforms inactive peptide angiotensin I into the potent hypertensive agent angiotensin II in the body. At the time Professor John Vane was studying some of the mechanisms involved in the control of hypertension and asked to assess whether BPF could interfere with ACE. BPF was found to be a strong ACE inhibitor and these new and interesting results encouraged John Vane to assess BPF as a new tool for development of a new drug to treat hypertension. At the time he was a consultant to the Squibb Pharmaceutical Company in New Jersey, USA. Vane suggested that Squibb should continue the pre-clinical and clinical studies of BPF to develop a new therapy to treat high blood pressure. After overcoming many challenges, in particular the need to convert the BPF peptide into a stable peptide for oral administration and develop large-scale method of synthesising this peptide, as well as the need for clinical research, captopril was finally approved by the FDA in the early 1980s (trade name capoten), allowing the company's first drug to sell one billion dollars. Currently there are about nine ACE inhibitors on the market and together their sales are worth more than 5 billion dollars per annum. In 1982 John Vane was awarded the Nobel Prize for Medicine and Physiology for his contributions to research on the mechanism of action of aspirin and other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and for the discovery of prostaglandins. Sergio spent many years working at the Vane's laboratory and co-authored many papers on these fields.

THE RELEVANCE OF BRAZILIAN BIODIVERSITY TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW COSMETICS

Few Brazilian scientists are currently interested in studying the Brazilian biome in order to develop innovative cosmetic products. However, the Brazilian cosmetic market has been growing at a high rate over the last decade, reaching annual sales of about 13 billion US dollars in 2016. There are 2,642 ANVISA-registered companies that sell cosmetics in Brazil. These companies are represented in almost all Brazilian states, except for the state of Roraima.

Amongst the many examples of plants native to Brazil that have been the source of innovative cosmetic products are babacú (*Orbignya speciosa*), murumuru (*Astrocaryum murumuru*), bacuri (*Platonia insignis*), buriti (*Mauritia flexuosa*), acaí (*Euterpe oleracea*), umbu and umbu-cajá (*Spondias tuberosa*). In 2008, through a partnership between Federal University of Santa Catarina, Financiadora de Estudos e Projetos (FINEP) and Natura cosmetic company, our group studied the standardised extract of the leaves of *Passiflora alata*, a native plant of Brazil. This project allowed Natura company to develop an innovative cosmetic product, named flavonoid of passiflora, that is still commercially available. The data discussed above suggest that scientific research on the Brazilian biome in partnership with the cosmetics industry should be encouraged, with the aim of developing innovative products.

Included Drugs and Jurisdictions

A retrospective analysis of EMA and HTA reports was performed. All drugs conditionally approved between March 2006 (the start date of the CMA scheme) and December 2018 were included. Included HTA organizations were major European HTA jurisdictions that systematically publish full initial HTA reports and reassessment reports on their websites in a language understood by the investigators, being: England + Wales (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, NICE), France (Haute Autorité de Santé, HAS), the Netherlands (Zorginstituut Nederland, ZIN) and the European Network for Health Technology Assessment (EUnetHTA). HTA reports were retrieved by searching agencies' websites for the drug generic and brand name and were included until June 2019, to allow time for HTA decision-making after drug approval. Vaccines were excluded because HTA organizations assess vaccines differently from other drugs.

Data Extraction

To investigate the role of SOBs in REAs, data was extracted for regulatory evaluations and HTA initial assessments and reassessments. We recorded general characteristics of drugs including drug name, indication, therapeutic category, orphan status at conditional approval, CMA date (European Commission decision), marketing authorization conversion date (if applicable), and whether the drug had undergone accelerated assessment by the EMA. Drug regulatory data on pivotal observational and interventional studies submitted for approval and to fulfil post-approval SOBs were retrieved from the European public assessment reports. The number of pivotal studies evaluated for approval of the drug and the included primary endpoints within these pivotal studies were recorded. Primary endpoints were categorized as

surrogate or clinical efficacy endpoints, or safety endpoints based on the information provided by the European public assessment report and on previous literature describing the type of endpoints in pivotal studies for conditionally approved drugs. Considering post-approval studies, all SOBs were extracted from EMA documents following previously published procedures.

The number of SOBs per drug and their original due dates and final submission dates (if applicable) were recorded. The objective of the SOB (addressing, efficacy, safety or other), type of obligation (clinical trial or other) and its status at approval were also recorded. Again, the primary endpoints for those SOBs entailing clinical trials were categorized as surrogate, clinical or safety.

Data on HTA considerations and conclusions regarding relative effectiveness were retrieved from published HTA reports – including initial assessments as well as reassessments – each matching the initial CMA indication. HTA recommendations that were not substantiated by a consideration of the clinical evidence were excluded (eg, a negative recommendation because no dossier was submitted by the manufacturer). When the CMA concerned multiple indications that were considered separately by HTA organizations, all were included independently. The same approach was applied when HTA organizations split a single indication into recommendations for 2 or more subpopulations. From HTA reports, the dates of the initial assessment and reassessments were recorded, as well as the outcome of the REA and whether the assessments included a discussion of the (lack of) results from completed SOBs.

Data Analysis

First, descriptive statistics were used to describe drug, pivotal study and SOB characteristics. Second, based on the dates of included HTA reports, SOB results were categorized as being available for HTA organizations (y/n) in initial REAs as well as in reassessments and it was analyzed whether available SOB results were included by HTA organizations. For initial REAs, the proportions of positive and negative recommendations were compared between those REAs including SOB results and those not including SOB results. To that end, the outcomes of the REAs were categorized into lesser effectiveness, equal effectiveness and higher effectiveness compared to jurisdiction-specific alternative treatments, in line with previous work. When REAs did not include SOBs even though they were already available at the time of HTA decision, it was assessed whether the REA process was already ongoing

when SOB results became available. If so, these indications were categorized as having no SOBs available yet.

Finally, the contributing role of SOB results was assessed by investigating the initial and reassessment REA reports for those drugs that had initial assessments that did not include results from SOBs while the reassessments did. HTA organizations' major concerns on the clinical evidence were extracted from the reports' summary statements. From the reassessment reports, statements were extracted about SOB results affecting the assessments and/or assessment outcomes by resolving or not resolving any or all of the major concerns. Major concerns were – in line with previous work – classified into categories related to the trial validity, the patient population, comparative effects, and the relevance of the endpoints and the drug's effect size on those endpoints. Possible changes to REA outcomes were assessed based on the REA categories used within each jurisdiction.

This study aimed to investigate if results from regulator-imposed post-approval studies (ie, SOBs) for conditionally approved drugs were used by HTA organizations within REAs and if so, how these studies have affected reassessments.

Our findings indicate that HTA organizations almost always included results of SOBs for conditionally approved drugs in their assessments, if those results were available at the time of assessment. However, these were only available in a minority of cases, because most initial REAs were performed before any results from SOBs were available. Furthermore, because HTA reassessments were relatively uncommon, most results from SOBs that became available after the initial HTA recommendation were not used within any REA.

In those cases where SOB results became available between the initial assessment and a reassessment, they had variable effects on HTA recommendations. In 4 cases (44%), SOB results directly led to reassessment conclusions that were different from the initial REA. A lack of established comparative effects was most often the major concern resolved by SOBs. In each case these concerns were resolved through newly initiated studies rather than continuations or extensions of pivotal trials. Depending on how convincing the effect sizes were in the SOB results in relation to what was hypothesized in the initial REA, the relative benefit was either upgraded or downgraded in the reassessment. In the other 5 cases, SOB results did not change the REA. In 2 cases this was because there were no major concerns to be solved by the SOB and in the other 3 cases the SOB results did not adequately resolve the

major concerns from the initial REA. For one of those 3 cases, the reassessment REA outcome was nonetheless different from the initial REA, due to factors independent of the assessed drug or the SOB results.

Implications

The lack of initial REAs that included SOB study results was expected given the sequence and timing of regulatory evaluations and HTAs in the drug lifecycle: most initial REAs are already finished by the time any post-approval study results become available. Current initiatives between the 2 stakeholders regarding data sharing and parallel evaluations will likely further shorten the timing between regulatory evaluations and HTA. To ensure incorporation of relevant post-approval study results in HTA decisions, a more systematic approach to reassessments by HTA organizations could therefore be appropriate. Currently, there is a clear misalignment between both stakeholders regarding post approval processes. Regulators review the CMA annually and aim to ultimately convert the CMA status to a standard marketing authorization, while HTA reassessments of relative effectiveness are scarce and rarely timed after the moment of conversion to standard marketing authorization.

Our results also indicate that large differences are present in the (re)assessment procedures of the included HTA organizations. HAS aims to evaluate all drugs, while NICE and ZIN have risk-based selection procedures to decide which drugs they will assess. HAS has a procedure for reassessments that dictates reassessments every 5 years, or when new evidence warrants it. However, the reassessments performed by HAS for our cohort of drugs often included only an assessment of the actual benefit (to determine whether the drug should remain on the positive reimbursement list), while no reevaluation of relative effectiveness was performed. Therefore we could not include these reassessments in our analysis. Similarly, NICE can set a date for reassessment during the initial evaluation when this is warranted, or, if no date is set, checks for new evidence every 5 years. Again, for the drugs included in our analysis often NICE screened the evidence and found a reassessment was not necessary. ZIN can reevaluate drugs, and had a reassessment procedure for a selection of (expensive) inpatient drugs from 2006-2014. No systematic reassessment procedure currently exists and reassessments are rare. Reassessments can also be requested by manufacturers, but because many initial REAs are already positive, there may not be many. Indeed, in our study, for most indications for which a reassessment was performed, the initial REA indicated a lack of or little added benefit. There might also be an underreporting of reassessments when REA outcomes remain

unchanged. Other factors, for example capacity restraints, may also contribute to the scarcity of reassessments. Further development of targeted reassessment processes – in line with the timing of evidence development and conversion of conditional to standard marketing authorization – for all HTA organizations can facilitate alignment between HTA reassessments and the CMA process of the EMA. Though EUnetHTA assessments for conditionally approved drugs were found to be extremely rare, EU net HTA has evaluated some CMA drugs approved after the inclusion timeframe of this study (eg, polatuzumab vedotin and crizanlizumab). Besides joint assessments, EU net HTA may play an important role in the standardization of reassessment processes throughout Europe. A good starting point may be the EUnetHTA report on the criteria to select and prioritize health technologies for additional evidence generation. Full alignment on reassessment processes is nevertheless unlikely for the near future because reassessments may also be triggered by cost aspects or by revisions to national confidential pricing arrangements or treatment guidelines.

The changes in HTA recommendations as a consequence of the availability of results from SOBs indicate that post approval evidence can be relevant for HTA organizations. However, our study also indicates that in some cases worries about the quality or relevance of SOB results limited their impact. Lack of study quality or inadequacies in the patient populations, comparators or endpoints have been shown to result in evidence not being helpful for the assessment of relative effectiveness. Previous studies have also highlighted that data requirements from HTA organizations often go beyond requests made by the EMA. Early agreement between regulators and HTA organizations regarding appropriate post-approval study requests could lead to study results that are more helpful for HTA organizations. It has already been shown that regulators and HTA organizations can agree on the most appropriate characteristics for preapproval studies. Possibly, a similar coordinated approach throughout the entire drug lifecycle could facilitate post approval evidence generation. However, firm conclusions about the potential impact of post-approval study results are impossible due to the small number of HTA reassessments. The adequate and timely completion of post-approval studies can be another area for coordination. Research has shown that SOBs are often delayed, changed, or not finished at all. Coordination between regulators and HTA organizations regarding timing and content of (re)evaluations could provide incentives for timely finishing SOBs. Such coordination requires HTA organizations to be free to vary their timing of reassessments.

This study focused solely on REAs, but HTA organizations have repeatedly emphasized that the limited evidence associated with conditionally approved drugs does not justify their high prices.^{29,30} Post-approval studies could influence the cost-effectiveness estimate as well as the uncertainty in that estimate by providing more information regarding the drug's relative effects. Indeed, the availability of more long term results within the crizotinib reassessment of NICE together with a renegotiation of the drug price led to the overall reimbursement recommendation going from negative to positive, even though the REA had been positive from the beginning. Already, many HTA organizations individually experiment with conditional financing schemes, but the results are mixed and their implementation is uncoordinated across countries.³¹ European coordination between regulators and HTA organizations could result in a joint definition of the necessary evidence to turn a conditional approval and conditional, limited reimbursement into a standard approval and full reimbursement.

Study design and sample

We used the Drugs@FDA database to identify all novel drugs approved by the FDA between 1 January 2005 and 31 December 2012 on the basis of either a single pivotal trial or pivotal trials focused on surrogate markers of disease, as described in previous work.³ Our sample included all new drug and biologic licensing applications for small molecule and biologic drugs, excluding generic drugs, reformulations, combination treatments of non-novel agents, and non-treatment agents such as diagnostic and contrast agents. Pivotal trials were those labeled as such in the FDA medical review. If the FDA review did not specify, we identified trials that were described as essential to approval, were otherwise prioritized in the review, or were new efficacy based trials provided as part of a resubmitted application for approval.

We also used the Drugs@FDA database to obtain the year of approval for each novel drug and whether it was considered a pharmacologic (small molecule) or biologic product. We used FDA approval letters, which are hyperlinked in the Drugs@FDA database, to identify orphan drugs, drugs approved through the accelerated approval pathway, and the indication for which all novel drugs were initially approved. Orphan drugs were those classified as such by the FDA, meaning drugs for rare diseases that were given extended market exclusivity. The Drugs@FDA database only indicates orphan status for biologics approved after 2010.

Indications were categorized by expected length of treatment using a previously developed framework:³ expected length of use of less than one month was acute, between one month

and two years was intermediate, and more than two years was chronic. We used the World Health Organization's anatomic therapeutic classification system, contextualized for clinical relevance, to categorize each indication into therapeutic areas,¹⁶ which we collapsed into four categories: cancer, cardiovascular disease and diabetes mellitus, infectious disease, and other.

Systematic review of post approval trials

Two investigators (AMP, JAA) systematically searched all fields of Medline for the international non-proprietary name of each drug to identify all post approval prospective studies in humans that used an active or placebo control and examined efficacy for the same indication for which the drug was first approved by the FDA. We searched for studies published between 1 January of the year before the drug was approved and 31 December 2014. This timeframe was chosen to find studies that started enrolling before FDA approval but did not produce data soon enough to be included in the FDA submission.

Although Medline is not a complete repository of all publications in all biomedical journals, it is the largest database of biomedical journal articles that can be searched freely using the PubMed system. Nearly all doctors and policy makers depend on it to learn about and obtain access to the findings of clinical trials.

Indications approved on the basis of surrogate markers We performed systematic reviews of the literature for all 49 indications for the 48 drugs that were approved by the FDA on the basis of multiple pivotal trials evaluating surrogate markers of disease. We identified a total of 554 published post approval controlled studies using an active or placebo control and examining efficacy for the same therapeutic indication for which the drug was first approved (table 2). Of these, 89.0% (n=493) were randomized, 51.8% (n=287) used open label allocation, 92.4% (n=512) used primary efficacy endpoints that were surrogate markers of disease, 65.9% (n=365) used an active drug as control, 88.8% (n=492) used a superiority design, and 60.8% (n=337) were funded by industry. The median overall intention to treat population was 127 (interquartile range 49-429), and median study duration was 24 weeks (8-48). Among the 325 superiority studies using active comparators, two of eight (25.0%) studies examining clinical efficacy endpoints reported positive results, whereas 143 of 317 (45.1%) of those examining surrogate markers reported positive results (table 3). Among the 139 superiority studies using placebo comparators, 50.0% (two of four) of clinical endpoint studies and 80.0% (108 of 135) of surrogate marker studies reported positive results.

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We aggregated studies by indication and found that the median number of post approval studies for each indication was 3 (interquartile range 1-8) (see supplementary appendix figure 1b), and the median number of randomized and double blind studies was 1 (0-3.5) (table 4). The median number of patients enrolled was 533 (122-3633), and the median number of patients in the intervention arm was 352 (104-2080) (see supplementary appendix figure 2b). The median number of patient years was 448.5 (23.1-2952.0), and the median number of intervention patient years was 350.0 (12.2-1412.8) (see supplementary appendix figure 3b). No post approval studies were identified for eight of 49 (16.3%) approved indications. Twenty eight indications (57.1%) had one or more post approval, randomized controlled, double blind positive study showing superior efficacy, one of which (2.0%) used a clinical outcome for the primary endpoint.

Indications Approved On The Basis Of A Single Pivotal Trial Evaluating Surrogate Markers

We performed systematic reviews of the literature for all 41 indications for the 40 drugs that were approved by the FDA on the basis of a single pivotal trial evaluating surrogate markers of disease. We identified a total of 127 published post approval controlled studies using an

active or placebo control and examining efficacy for the supplementary appendix figure 3c). No post approval studies were identified for 20 of 41 (48.8%) approved indications. Six indications (14.6%) had one or more post approval, randomized controlled, double blind positive study showing superior efficacy, two of which (4.9%) used a clinical outcome for the primary endpoint.

We found substantial variation in the quantity and quality of studies of novel drugs published after they were approved by the FDA on the basis of a single pivotal trial, pivotal trials that used surrogate markers of disease, or both. We found few published randomized controlled, double blind studies showing superior efficacy based on clinical outcomes that examined the same indication for which the drug was first approved by the FDA after a median follow-up of 5.5 years. These findings have important implications for clinical care. Both doctors and patients have high expectations for the safety and efficacy of a drug approved by the FDA. But less than one third of new drug indications approved by the FDA on the basis of a single pivotal trial had at least one post approval trial showing superior efficacy; even fewer used clinical outcomes. Similarly, less than one 10th of new drug indications approved by the FDA on the basis of surrogate markers of disease had at least one post approval trial validating the use of the surrogate marker by showing superior efficacy using clinical outcomes. Our work corresponds with a previous study demonstrating that highly cited studies are infrequently followed by subsequent clinical studies that confirm original effects and is consistent with a study showing that cancer drugs approved on the basis of surrogate markers are infrequently followed by clinical studies demonstrating improved overall survival.

As well as finding few robustly designed, confirmatory studies, we also found noticeable variability in the degree to which novel drugs were studied in the post approval period, both within and between the categories of approval. Although a small number of approved indications had dozens of qualifying post approval studies, more than one third had no published post approval controlled studies investigating efficacy. Furthermore, across approval categories, the studies showed statistically significant differences in all features of trial design, except randomization, as well as in aggregated median numbers of studies and in patient enrollment.

For many novel drugs, the problem is not that post approval studies are poorly designed or have negative efficacy results, but rather that they are not being published or performed at all. Our findings are consistent with previous studies showing that even post approval studies

required by the FDA to be conducted by manufacturers are not always performed in a timely manner and with previous work demonstrating the variability in the number and completion of post marketing studies of high risk medical devices.

The majority of the post approval studies that we identified focused on surrogate markers of disease. Using surrogate markers instead of clinical outcomes for trial endpoints has become increasingly controversial, with several approved drugs ultimately failing to confirm any clinical benefit and an analysis of oncology surrogate markers finding variable correlation with overall survival. Surrogate markers have been used for pivotal clinical studies to facilitate more rapid regulatory evaluation, with the expectation that subsequent clinical studies will focus on clinical outcomes. We found that this occurs infrequently, as approximately 90% of post approval studies of drugs for indications approved on the basis of surrogate markers also used surrogate markers of disease for trial endpoints.

Recent proposals for FDA reform include creating a comprehensive benefit and risk assessment and management plan to be updated at regular intervals and with any shift in a drug's benefit to risk profile⁷; increasing reliance on surrogate markers, smaller and shorter trials, and evidence derived from registries and observational studies; and switching to a "consumer reports" approach of grades for efficacy, safety, and degree of evidence. Our findings show that caution would be needed for these approaches—high quality post approval evidence does not necessarily accumulate and may require additional regulatory requirements. To strengthen lifecycle evaluation of recently approved drugs, requirements for post approval studies might need to be heightened or might need to specify study design characteristics or trial endpoints in detail to ensure that these studies provide high quality evidence to further inform clinical practice. Of course, it must be remembered that publishing one short term, small post approval study might be inadequate for a hypertension drug but entirely reasonable for one treating a rare disease. A customized, specific plan for post approval studies will be key to generating an adequate amount of post approval evidence on comparative efficacy, which should take into consideration disease prevalence and severity, the drug's anticipated length of use, and the availability of other treatment options.

CONCLUSIONS

Trials are usually powered to detect benefit and seldom designed with adverse events as primary outcome. It is not possible to design trials to evaluate unexpected or unknown adverse effects that have yet to be linked to the intervention. Clinical trials should include

explicit pre specified monitoring of pharmacologically predictable adverse events and ensure adequate follow-up of withdrawn participants. Recent regulatory guidance from the FDA has limited the reporting of adverse events in clinical trials from sponsors to those that are unexpected and considered related to the drug. It is unclear how isolated investigators will determine the causal relationship between a drug and its adverse events. The expanding role of electronic trials registers with detailed study results has potential that can only be fully realized when sponsors provide reliable, accurate and complete data. Empirical work is needed to evaluate whether novel approaches such as mechanism-based drug toxicity prediction can complement safety data from clinical trials and improve an assessment of drug safety. Methodological research is needed to determine whether network meta-analysis techniques can provide reliable and valid comparative evaluation of drug safety. The European Medicines Agency has recently undertaken methodological work to enhance the consistency and transparency of their risk-benefit decision-making process. Current proposals emphasize the need to not just consider the magnitude and consequences of treatment effects, but also to evaluate less tangible factors such as the level of uncertainty and extent of risk tolerance. These developments are particularly relevant when considering rare but serious adverse events where the clinical trials may yield imprecise or even conflicting estimates. Multi-criteria decision analytical techniques that accurately capture quantitative inputs and qualitative values from various stakeholders for risk-benefit trade-offs and allow for quantitative analysis and modelling uncertainty on a range of outcomes can improve complex regulatory decisions about drug safety.

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